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Edge Data Plane Programmability for Robotic Control Application Latency Improvements

**Programabilidade de Planos de Dados de Borda para
Aperfeiçoamento de Latência de Aplicações de Controle
Robótico**

Campinas
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“An expert is a person who has made all the mistakes that can be made in a very narrow field.”
(Niels Bohr)

Abstract

For some time now, software-defined networks (Software-Defined Networking (SDN)) have been a widely known approach that seeks to turn computer networks more flexible. Interest continues to increase due to features such as the programmability for the data plane that aims to perform more complex functions at the stack level. The (Programmable Protocol-Independent Packet Processors (P4)) is the reference language that describes how packets should be processed within the data plane. Software-defined networks' benefits in performing critical services directly in the data plane have attracted attention in different areas, including Industrial Networks, Internet of Things (IoT), and robotics.

With the arrival of new technologies such as cloud computing, other emerging technologies are appearing, like cloud robotics, where some traditional robot applications are moving to the cloud, typically migrating to an edge or core data center to leverage the powerful resources that these can offer. In that context, traditional robot controllers are now running in the cloud that offers machine-learning processes and enables advanced control techniques to monitor robots, identify sudden changes in a workstation, and promptly generate preventive actions to avoid undesirable risks (e.g., collisions). These critical scenarios, low latency, and high availability are essential for applications. However, network infrastructure supporting robot and data center communication is undetermined; network traffic issues (e.g., packet loss, delays) or congestions can appear on these links and be a challenge and impact the correct functionality of applications.

This work identifies two potential scenarios for robotic control application latency improvements. In our first scenario, we propose to improve the timing response for a stop emergency action sent from a robot controller in the cloud. To this end, we propose to use an edge programmable data plane near the robot and use it to offload stop action and generate action messages to respond to the robot. In our second scenario, we identify that monitoring techniques implemented directly in the data plane can provide comprehension of network behavior, such as identifying congestions on the data center links that run robot applications. In this line, we propose to use a programmable data plane to minimize congestion by monitoring those links and identifying and selecting the suitable one that can offer better conditions to send the traffic. Each use case is covered independently in different chapters. Final notes on lessons learned, conclusions, limitations, and future work are also covered below for each use case.

Keywords: Latency; Programmable Data Planes; Robotic.

Resumo

Desde há algum tempo, as redes definidas por software (SDN) são uma abordagem amplamente conhecida que busca tornar as redes de computadores mais flexíveis. O interesse continua aumentando devido a recursos como a programabilidade para o plano de dados que visa executar funções mais complexas no nível da pilha de dados. P4 é a linguagem de referência que descreve como os pacotes devem ser processados dentro do plano de dados. Os benefícios das redes definidas por software na execução de serviços críticos diretamente no plano de dados têm atraído atenção em diferentes áreas, incluindo Redes Industriais, Internet das Coisas (IoT) e robótica.

Com a chegada de novas tecnologias, como a computação em nuvem, outras tecnologias emergentes estão aparecendo, como a robótica em nuvem, onde alguns aplicativos de robôs tradicionais estão se movendo para a nuvem, normalmente migrando para um data center de borda ou core para aproveitar os recursos poderosos que eles podem oferecer. Nesse contexto, os controladores de robôs tradicionais agora estão sendo executados na nuvem que oferece processos de aprendizado de máquina e permite avançadas técnicas de controle para monitorar os robôs e identificar mudanças repentinas em uma estação de trabalho e gerar prontamente ações preventivas para evitar riscos indesejáveis (por exemplo, colisões). Esses cenários críticos, baixa latência e alta disponibilidade são essenciais para os aplicativos. No entanto, a infraestrutura de rede que suporta a comunicação do robô e do data center é indeterminada; problemas de tráfego de rede (por exemplo, perda de pacotes, atrasos) ou congestionamentos podem aparecer nesses links e ser um desafio e afetar a funcionalidade correta dos aplicativos.

Este trabalho identifica dois cenários potenciais para melhorias na latência de aplicações de controle robótico. Em nosso primeiro cenário, propomos melhorar o tempo de resposta para uma ação de parada de emergência enviada por um controlador de robô na nuvem. Para isso, propomos usar um plano de dados programável de borda próximo ao robô e usá-lo para descarregar a ação de parada e gerar mensagens de ação para responder ao robô. Em nosso segundo cenário, identificamos que as técnicas de monitoramento implementadas diretamente no plano de dados podem fornecer compreensão do comportamento da rede, como identificar congestionamentos nos links do data center que executam aplicativos dos robôs. Nesta linha, propomos a utilização de um plano de dados programável para minimizar o congestionamento monitorando esses enlaces e identificando e selecionando aquele adequado que possa oferecer melhores condições para enviar o tráfego. Cada caso de uso é abordado independentemente em diferentes capítulos. Notas finais sobre lições aprendidas, conclusões, limitações e trabalho futuro também são abordadas abaixo para cada caso de uso.

Palavras-chave: Latência; Plano de Dados Programável; Robótica.

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Acronyms

5G Fifth Generation Mobile Network. 21

ACK Acknowledgement. 39, 40, 43, 44, 55

ACL Access Control Lists. 22, 23

AR Augmented Reality. 33

BGP Border Gateway Protocol. 23, 24

BLE Bluetooth Low Energy. 35

BLESS Bluetooth Low Energy Service Switch. 35

BM Behavioral Model. 27

BMv1 Behavioral Model Version 1. 27

BMv2 Behavioral Model Version 2. 27, 43

CP Control Plane. 20, 22

DDoS Distributed Denial-of-Service. 33, 34

DOF Degree of Freedom. 17, 31, 41, 44

DP Data Plane. 21–24

DT Digital Twin. 33

FPGA Field Programmable Gate Array. 24

GUI Graphical User Interface. 29

HW Hardware. 24

IaaS Infrastructure as a Service. 28

IIoT Industrial IoT. 18, 34

IoRT Internet of Robotic Things. 17–19

IoT Internet of Things. viii, ix, 28, 33, 35

IP Internet Protocol. 30, 44, 47

IPv4 Internet Protocol version 4. 22, 23, 47

IPv6 Internet Protocol version 6. 22, 23

JSON JavaScript Object Notation. 27

MPLS Multiprotocol Label Switching. 23, 24

NFC Network Function Cloudification. 28

NFV Network Function Virtualization. 28, 38, 56

NIC Network Interface Card. 23

OSPF Open Shortest Path First. 23, 24

P4 Programmable Protocol-Independent Packet Processors. viii, ix, 18–20, 22–24, 26, 27, 33–37, 40–47, 49, 59, 60, 65, 69

PaaS Platform as a Service. 28

PDP Programmable Data Plane. 20, 36, 41

PISA Protocol Independent Switch Architecture. 22, 23

QoE Quality of Experience. 28, 56

QoS Quality of Service. 56

RTP Real-time Transport Protocol. 68

RTT Round-Trip Time. 19, 28, 33, 35, 55, 56, 58–61

SaaS Software as a Service. 28

SDN Software-Defined Networking. viii, ix, 18, 20, 21, 23, 27, 36, 38, 49

SEQ Sequence. 39, 40, 43, 44

SLA Service-Level Agreement. 28, 56

SP Service Provider. 28

SW Software. 24

SYN Synchronize. 55

TCP Transfer Control Protocol. 30, 34, 35, 39–44, 46, 47, 49, 59–61

ULL Ultra-low Latency. 43

UR Universal Robot. 29, 30

UR10 Universal Robot UR10. 20, 29, 31, 41, 44

UR3 Universal Robot UR3. 29, 31

UR5 Universal Robot UR5. 29, 31

URScript Universal Robot Script. 29, 30, 44

URSim Universal Robot Simulator. 29–31, 39–42

VM Virtual Machine. 29

VNF Virtual Network Function. 28

VR Virtual Reality. 33

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Chapter 1

Introduction

From time to time, an industrial revolution changes the industrial processes, output, and productivity profoundly, as well as the business operation of most countries around the world [1]. The industrial revolution began in the late 18th century with mechanical production plants based on water and steam energy; here, the first steam machines emerged. At the end of the 19th century, the second industrial revolution began, allowing mass production to be developed based on electrical energy. The third industrial revolution began in the middle of the 20th century; the significant advances in electronics and computerized systems allowed introduce robots to production processes [2]. Nowadays, we are living in the fourth industrial revolution, also known as Industry 4.0, which is characterized by a fusion of technologies that offer more interlinked automation, machine learning, and real-time data to the manufacturing industry [3]. Traditionally, industrial manufacturing systems have relied on industrial robots to perform specific and repetitive tasks [4]. With this digital transformation of manufacturing, the robotics area has reaped enormous benefits; for instance, industrial robots with high Degree of Freedom (DOF) are more lightweight, intelligent, and flexible than their predecessors decades ago [5]. Also, with an emphasis on service task applications, robotic manipulators are implementing new machine-learning algorithms and advanced control techniques for trajectory tracking of robots to reach highly accurate robotic control [6].

Furthermore, embedded sensors (e.g., temperature sensor, high definition camera, distance sensor) incorporated in collaborative robots help to improve the way to work side by side with humans by detecting sudden changes (e.g., fortuitous movements or obstacles) in the collaborative workspace [7]. In this line, the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) can contribute to reducing accidents in industrial manufacturing works. However, at critical moments, with no reaction in time (e.g., emergency stop), the consequences can be collisions, damage to the actuator, or even human injury. To address these unexpected events and monitor robot performance, they are connected to powerful controllers for continuous monitoring and swift and precise interventions (e.g., sending an emergency stop signal). These days, with an emphasis on service task applications, robotic controllers are allocated to run on cloud infrastructures to leverage the cloud's scalability, processing, and storage.

Cloud data centers support this emerging cloud adoption process for robotic applications. These data centers incorporate a vast formation of servers to provide a wide range of services to various needs, such as instructions from the cloud and data insights. Edge and core data centers are two types of data centers with different purposes for delivering cloud services. An edge data center is suitable for time-sensitive scenarios; it is geographically located closer to the source

of data generated; therefore, data is processed on the edge. Despite these data centers being beneficial for real-time data processing closer to end-user (e.g., robots), they are more limited regarding resources and scalability. A core data center removes those limitations and offers a high capacity for massive computing, storage of large volumes of data, and high availability to large-scale applications and services. Nonetheless, remote end-users may experience higher latency in accessing applications and services compared to an edge data center. Computer networking plays a crucial role in supporting end-to-end communication between applications, services, and end-user. Networking devices such as routers and switches enable the bi-directional forwarding of messages for both ends. However, in the IoRT, network infrastructure needs to deal with applications such as industrial control requiring ultra-low latency in data transmission to respond instantaneously to a request or event. For instance, applications in robotic control demand high reliability, availability, and extremely low latency [8]; a suitable threshold for this scenario can be in the range of a few milliseconds [9].

SDN is a well-known solution proposed for the network management of time-sensitive applications [10, 11], SDN separates the control and data plane and enables the programmability on both planes [12]. This successful paradigm shift has recently started to captivate other areas, including industry 4.0 and robotic control [13] facilitating conditions to centralize each robot controller and to improve operational management significantly (e.g., controller programming). With the evolution of SDN [10], the advances in programmable data planes are more noteworthy these days. Orient with the progress; different approaches are considered by the research community, including migrating to emerging programmable networks. To this end is needed a programming language like P4, a domain-specific language with features that helps to disaggregate the network stack [14]. P4 offers new opportunities to specify the packet processing logic inside network datapath pipelines based on a programmable parser and a pipeline of match+action tables.

At this time, in Industrial IoT (IIoT) and IoRT, innovation is fueling unprecedented growth, and the tending is to continue to assign thousands of applications and services to be allocated in the cloud, turning it into an operational and management environment for end-users. From a network perspective, applications and services are becoming more sophisticated daily and require more suitable infrastructure to support current and upcoming innovations. This leads to increased difficulty in providing good-performing with lower latency for time-sensitive applications that can be drastically affected in terms of performance when exposed to network traffic problems (e.g., jitter, packet loss, delays), frequently present in a network, even from the end-user perspective, the chances of something being wrong could be higher when the network suffers delays to respond in time to a request or event. Therefore, this work aims for time-sensitive particular application latency improvements. To this end, we explore one of the currently hottest areas, such as industrial networks. For our approach, we propose to use programmable data planes and P4 to offload applications and server functions in the network. We objectively identify two time-sensitive use case scenarios to introduce and use a P4 data plane to address the low latency needed. We design, implement and validate those approaches.

For the first scenario, we explore latency-critical applications in industrial robotic control. This use case is an approach to offloading robotic control functions to an edge programmable data plane device. This in-network P4-based solution mainly aims to perform as an edge robot control for vital actions such as an emergency stop. Using P4, we can implement a simple logic inside the datapath pipeline to process tasks like matching a threshold position calculation. This use case engages a traditional robotic control scenario to emergency stop a robot from a controller working on the cloud. We demonstrated that traditional robotic control may produce

many disadvantages for a time-sensitive application, especially by suffering drastically in terms of network latency. We also showed that latency can be handled best by performing in-network robot control in the edge P4 device. To reach this end, we explore the kinematic configuration of the robot and network performance issues to analyze how parameters such as the robot acceleration or delays in a link can affect generated messages by the robot controller through the network, even when quick actions are required. However, this work has some limitations to being a complete solution for edge robot control, such as running in a virtual environment and considering just a few basic tasks that allow controlling the robot in a non-real situation. Some issues need to be handled, including real-time control and the robot's kinematic configuration, towards better notions on how P4 contributes to the performance application on the network to take any action on time. For this use case, we explore the opening work In-network P4-based low latency robot arm control [15].

In our second use case, we put more effort into handling the traffic generated between the end user and the cloud applications and services. Indeed, areas such as industrial networks are gaining more interest in cloudification. Recently, new applications for cloud robotics and IoRT are adding up to a cloud that often uses robust data centers to run their applications. The rise of new time-sensitive applications in the cloud not only increases the need for a robust network infrastructure to handle a vast amount of cloud-based traffic but to provide low-latency links to support cloud applications effectively and, in addition, more accurate ways to track the traffic flow on these links to avoid network traffic issues such as congestion that can significantly impact the performance and user experience of cloud applications. In this second scenario, we explore network monitoring techniques to measure RTT metrics in TCP traffic directly in the data plane using P4. To this end, we validate the logic from work in Measuring TCP Round-Trip Time in the Data Plane [16] for a data center selection scenario. This work introduces an algorithm to passively monitor the Round-Trip Time (RTT) metric directly in the data plane. Towards that end, we can track RTT values in TCP connections. High values of RTT can indicate signals of performance issues in the network (e.g., congestion). This solution aims to be used for cloud robotic applications running on edge or core data centers and using the P4 device to reroute traffic to the one that offers lower latency.

Summarizing the contributions in this thesis, we propose application latency improvements by using edge programmable data planes in robotic control applications. Scenarios are presented independently, considering a complete approach (design, implementation, evaluation, limitations, future works), but both are aligned with the purpose of our research. The rest of this work contains the following topics: background information and discussion of related work are presented in Chapter 2. We aboard each use case independently examined, and each one brings the design goal, problem statement, research objectives, and methodology, and discuss the limitations and directions of future work. Then, the design and implementation of Low-latency Edge Robot Control with P4 datapaths are discussed in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 addresses guidelines to Programmable Edges for Data Center selection based on Flow RTT metrics. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes the thesis.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter introduces background concepts about our research and reviews relevant literature of the related works of this thesis, summarizing the more prominent aspects.

2.1 Background

This section defines the main concepts involved in our research work. Initiating in this chapter, we cover SDN, Data Plane Programmability in SDN, P4 as a programming language for Programmable Data Plane (PDP), Programming and compiling of a P4 target. We also discuss some highlight points to address the use cases in this work, including networking concepts such as traffic monitoring and new trends such as cloudification from the perspective of robotics. In addition, we introduce two powerful tools to simulate virtual robots, Universal Robot UR10 (UR10) as an industrial-robot arm and a robot controller concept.

2.1.1 Software-Defined Networking

SDN appears due to a long history of multiple efforts to put computer networks and programmability concepts together [17]. Along the way, SDN brought essential breakthroughs to the research community and, recently, to the market. This new paradigm highlights a new way to design and manage networks, offerings promising aspects such as decoupling the Control Layer from the Forwarding Layer, a key desired factor towards programmability and flexibility in the computer networks [10]. An SDN network architecture widely accepts three layers [18]: application, control, and forwarding. Figure 2.1 shows a simplified view of an SDN layer architecture.

1. **Application Layer** knows network needs and requirements. Enables developing and executing network applications (e.g., network monitoring, network policies) to provide solutions.
2. **Control Layer** or widely known as Control Plane (CP), holds an SDN controller, which is the network brain. Based on network application requirements, the controller deploys the control logic rules on the whole network and configures the network devices using a northbound interface for upper communication (application layer) and a southbound interface for lower communication (forwarding layer).

3. **Forwarding Layer**, better-known as Data Plane (DP), is composed of all infrastructures network equipment (e.g., routers, switches). DP is commonly associated with the feature of forwarding traffic.

Figure 2.1: Simplified View of an SDN Layer Architecture. Source: Adapted from [10]

2.1.2 Data Plane Programmability in SDN

With the vastly large number of network applications moving to the cloud [19], the onset of the Fifth Generation Mobile Network (5G) that promises faster speed and low latency for a great density of users and heavy traffic [20], new challenges appeared. Dedicated hardware, such as switches and routers, seems not to be adequate to cover an evolving world's demand for heterogeneous network functions such as in-network processing, load balancing, congestion control, tunneling, and so on. Vendors are frequently under a push to give support to these wide features required. Support forthcoming applications involves efficiency and flexibility on the part of the network devices. To overcome such limitations has been considered an SDN-based proposal, and a new generation of programmable network devices has been launched [21].

As mentioned above, SDN decouples the control plane from the data plane, a key aspect that provides flexibility for a programmable network [22]. Increasing worldwide adoption of this paradigm is emerging. However, recent studies show that frequent interactions between the data plane and control plane can bring unexpected delays to the network [23]. Besides, experiments show by using in-network hardware, some network functions can be offloaded to programmable data plane devices to perform in-network computation [15]. This novel architecture is called a stateful data plane [24].

The network devices of the new generation bring the ability to configure the network's behavior based on programmability. Previously SDN, the architecture used a stateless data plane only for forwarding packets. Nowadays, switching chips boost the packet-processing functionality by

using a top-down approach; software defines hardware actions. New chips are building based on Protocol Independent Switch Architecture (PISA) [25] for programming packet processing. Vendors have based their solutions on this innovative switch architecture [26]. Figure 2.2 shows the pipeline for a PISA switch chip. It is composed of three portions: programmable parser, programmable match-action pipeline, and programmable deparser. A programmable datapath is defined based on packet processing. When a packet enters, the programmable parser turns that packet into a set of headers (e.g., Ethernet header, IPv4 header), then headers move to the programmable match-action pipeline to perform a match and execute an action; this process goes for as many stages are included in the pipeline. After each step, the packet goes to the programmable deparser to put together its headers. Finally, the packet is sent out of the device.

Figure 2.2: Pipeline Forwarding Architecture. Source: Adapted from [25]

A PISA device offers the characteristic to define and customize a network protocol. To outgrow protocol independence, advances in languages for programming a programmable switch chip are also being incited by PISA programmable pipeline architecture. The top of Figure 2.3 represents the logical dataplane view. Initially, the device does not recognize what it is processing. Network protocols must be programmed to be recognized by the device. The programmer can write a program with network protocols, like L2, Internet Protocol version 4 (IPv4), Internet Protocol version 6 (IPv6), and Access Control Lists (ACL).

2.1.3 Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors

The approaching applications (e.g., edge computing, internet of things) require network devices, such as switches and routers, to support continuously evolving protocols [21]. Data plane programmability introduced a new generation of programmable network equipment, permitting the packet processing functionality to be reconfigured on the fly to address the required flexibility, performance, and efficiency requires [27]. A programmable device represents the next achievement in enabling switches to perform complex operations on packets using programming language [28].

Recently, many solutions have been proposed to make the network programmable and stateful. Among them, Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors (P4) [29]. P4 cannot describe the CP process. P4 was designed as an intuitive declarative language to describe how packets should be processed inside the DP of a programmable device. In 2014 was introduced *P4₁₄*, the previous release of P4. The P4 language consortium [30] launched an official specification; version 1.0.5 was the last released update [31]. Since 2018, the community is not

Figure 2.3: Protocol-Independent Switch Architecture. Source: Adapted from [25]

supporting $P4_{14}$. However, the latest update is still available on the language consortium website. The current release of the P4 language is $P4_{16}$. This specification has broadened to be implemented in a large variety of programmable network elements such as hardware or software switches, Network Interface Cards (NICs), or routers. Its scope indicates the syntax, semantic rules, and requirements for proper implementation of the latest available version, released in 2020 [32].

P4 gets to describe the packet processing pipeline in the DP by using the PISA programmable pipeline architecture. On top of the Figure 2.4 there is a schematic, where L2, IPv4, IPv6, and ACL are the representation of a P4 program. These protocols represent the logical dataplane view from the P4 program. Protocols added in the program are mapped onto the device stages, as shown at the bottom. Besides, the programmer can define a custom protocol in a program, P4 capabilities can also map a custom program.

OpenFlow [33] is a well-known SDN control protocol. However, limitations like minor support to a few header types impede flexibility towards the network automation. P4 has been raised as a proposal to fill the gap of OpenFlow limitations, focused on three goals:

1. **Reconfigurability in the field:** Programmers are able to redefine the packet processing once deployed.
2. **Protocol independence:** P4 program can easily add new protocols (e.g., Border Gateway Protocol (BGP), Open Shortest Path First (OSPF), Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS)) in the logical dataplane. Targets are not tied with a specific header type.
3. **Target independence:** A program can support target-independent implementation,

Figure 2.4: Switch Pipeline. Source: Adapted from [25]

which means that the same program can run on a large variety of targets, including Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), Hardware (HW), and Software (SW) switches.

Based on the proposed goals, it is possible to identify exciting benefits for DP programmability, essentially:

- Easily can be added new features (e.g., MPLS, OSPF, BGP)
- By having the ability to program the data plane and add new features, programmers can also remove unused features, using space properly.
- Programmers have the liberty to create custom protocols.
- Capability to monitor the header of packets. It can help to determine network latency.

The following parts can structure a P4 program:

1. **Header definitions**, express the sequence and structure for the format of the headers (see listing 2.1).

```

1 header_type IPv4.t {
2   fields {
3     version : 4;           // IP version 4
4     ihl : 4;              // IP header length
5     diffserv : 8;         // Type of service
6     totalLen : 16;        // Length of header
7     identification : 16;  // Unique packet id
8     flags : 3;
9     fragOffset : 13;      // Number of data bytes

```

```

10     ttl : 8;           // Time to live
11     protocol : 8;
12     hdrChecksum : 16; // Header checksum
13     srcAddr : 32;     // Source IP address
14     dstAddr : 32;     // Destination IP address
15     options : 32;     // Optional information
16 }
17 }
18 header IPv4_t IPv4;

```

Listing 2.1: P4 header declaration example

2. **Metadata**, contains information that is not treated by the packet data (see listing 2.2).

```

1 header_type local_metadata_t {
2     fields {
3         cpu_code : 16; // Code for packet going to CPU
4         port_type : 4; // Type of port
5         ingress_error : 1; // An error in ingress port check
6         was_mtagged : 1; // Track if pkt was mtagged on ingr
7         copy_to_cpu : 1; // Special code resulting in copy to CPU
8         bad_packet : 1; // Other error indication
9     }
10 }
11 metadata local_metadata_t local_metadata;

```

Listing 2.2: P4 metadata declaration example

3. **Counters, Meters, and Registers**, in conjunction, are also called stateful memories. Maintain state independent of packets (see listing 2.3)

```

1 counter ip_pkts_by_dest {
2     type : packets;
3     direct : ip_host_table;
4 }

```

Listing 2.3: P4 counter definition example

Another example(see listing 2.4).

```

1 meter customer_meters {
2     type : bytes;
3     instance_count : 1000;
4 }

```

Listing 2.4: P4 meter definition example

4. **Packet parser specification**, that allows how to identify header sequences within packets. A Parsed Representation of the packet is compared with the match values to apply an action (see listing 2.5).

```

1 parser start {
2     return parse_ethernet;
3 }
4
5 parser parse_ethernet {
6     extract(ethernet);
7     return select(latest.etherType) {
8         0x0800 : parse_ipv4;
9         default: ingress; }

```

```

10 }
11
12 parser parse_ipv4 {
13     extract(ipv4);
14     return ingress;
15 }

```

Listing 2.5: P4 parser example

5. **Match-action table specification**, linking packet and metadata fields to the match values and generating actions in response.

```

1 table sendout {
2     reads {
3         standard_metadata.egress_port : exact;
4     }
5     actions {
6         on_miss;
7         rewrite_src_mac;
8     }
9     size : 512;
10 }

```

Listing 2.6: P4 Match-action table specification example

6. **Actions**, declared as functions within match+actions tables. Each entry invokes an associated action.

```

1 action on_miss() {
2 }
3
4 action rewrite_src_mac(smac) {
5     modify_field(ethernet.srcAddr, smac);
6 }

```

Listing 2.7: P4 actions specification example

7. **Control flow**, describing the order of execution sequence tables applied to a packet.

```

1 control ingress {
2     apply(sendout);
3 }

```

Listing 2.8: P4 control flow specification example

In Figure 2.5 is represented the P4 abstract forwarding model. The pipeline is defined through a parser, a series of match+action tables that execute one or more actions (e.g., packet forwarding), and deparser functional blocks. When a packet ingress, the headers are parsed, then pass through match+actions tables to finally the deparser writes the header fields back and sends the packet to the output port [34]. P4 allows defining all these activities inside the ingress and egress of control flows.

2.1.4 Programming a P4 target

P4 is a high-level programming language that is not recognizable for the target language. It is required an action to transform code written in P4 into machine code. Consequently, a compiler is a computer program able to take that action, turning code readable at the lower level. Despite

Figure 2.5: P4 Abstract Forwarding Model. Source: Adapted from [28]

this, the compiler can not fix errors in the program (e.g., syntax); after compilation, it shall display all errors. Figure 2.6 represents the process flow to load a P4 program onto a target.

Figure 2.6: P4 Flow Process.

2.1.4.1 Compiler P4C

To offer a reference compiler for P4 was released the `p4c-behavioral`¹, also called Behavioral Model Version 1 (BMv1). This compiler is the first reference version for the Behavioral Model (BM) target. It generates a C file according to the given P4 input [35]. Some prerequisites, like `p4-hlir`² are needed to compile a program. However, `p4-hlir` is written in Python and only supports the $P4_{14}$ version. P4 programs written under $P4_{16}$ specification can not be compiled with BMv1, this turned into motivation to replace it with a new version.

2.1.4.2 Behavioral Model Version 2 (BMv2)

BMv2³ is the current reference P4 software switch developing as an open-source tool for testing P4 programs written either $P4_{14}$ or $P4_{16}$. The P4 used compiler for this new version of the virtual switch is the `p4c-bm2-ss`, an alias given to the `p4c-behavioral`. Figure 2.6 shows the compiling process. Initially, the programmer defines a P4 program (e.g., `helloworld.p4`), and the program is given as an input to the `p4c-bm2-ss` to be compiled. It produces a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file (e.g., `helloworld.json`) with the same name as the P4 file. The new file is used as an input in the P4 target to implement the packet-processing behavior specified by that P4 program. BMv2 is supported by Mininet⁴, a widely used emulator for SDN networks.

¹<https://github.com/p4lang/p4c-behavioral>

²<https://github.com/p4lang/p4-hlir>

³<https://github.com/p4lang/behavioral-model>

⁴<http://mininet.org/>

Figure 2.7: P4 Flow Compiling.

2.1.5 Network Monitoring

Corporate world networks demand high availability and performance. These days, as never before, it is essential to understand suitably the behavior of a network. Network monitoring gives a heightened perspective to network operators that continuously face network threats (e.g., traffic bottlenecks) [36]. At present more endpoints are connecting to an accelerated growing network boosted by a robust infrastructure of data centers; on the other hand, we can also interpret this scenario as an attractive environment more prone to failures (e.g., delays). Network latency is an indicator to determine the Quality of Experience (QoE) of the users in the network. RTT is a metric for network latency to express the amount of time taken for a packet to get from the source to the destination and back. An efficient RTT monitoring would provide to Service Providers (SPs) a significant comprehension for security and performance of the network traffic [37]. However, continuous monitoring of big data centers is costly. Recently, some efforts [19] are addressing evaluations to reach the best performance diagnosis for RTT measurements that are also guiding to benefits like detecting violations of Service-Level Agreement (SLA).

2.1.6 Cloudification

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) paved the way to implement in software architecture Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) (e.g., firewall, load balancer) traditionally implemented in dedicated hardware [38]. This approach brings a new trend to evolve from virtualization to cloudification, Network Function Cloudification (NFC) [39]. Cloud computing [40] and Edge computing [41] are two paradigms to process the increasing amount of data [42] (e.g., resources and application services). Cloud computing can be provided in three different models: Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) to cover the on-demand cloud applications. Generally, cloud applications run on containers hosted by robust data centers located so far from the endpoint. New trends such as IoT, Autonomous Vehicles are demanding real-time computing. Edge computing tries to fill the gap by bringing computing right next to the device by using Edge data centers to reduce processing times and improve application performance. However, those data centers are not as powerful as core datacenters [43].

2.1.6.1 Cloud Robotics

A well-known field such as robotics is setting its sight on cloudification. Recently, new initiatives such as cloud robotics [44] have been released, looking to deploy an internet for robots to allow them to communicate and share information. Figure 2.8 illustrates a high-level overview of the cloud robotic architecture. The top shows a cloud representation; cloud robotics applications (e.g., manufacture, service robotics, navigation) are hosted here, running instead of core or edge servers. The bottom side includes the endpoints (e.g., robots, drones). Endpoints are limited in terms of computing ability and data storage. Cloud fills this gap and offers unlimited computing and storage, bringing new opportunities for different verticals such as Industry 4.0.

Figure 2.8: Conventional cloud robotic architecture. Source: Adapted from [45]

2.1.7 URSim

Universal Robot (UR) is one of the leaders in collaborative robot vendors. They developed a robot simulator, nicknamed Universal Robot Simulator (URSim). This virtual representation of a real robot arm is provided for free. It can be downloaded at [46]. URSim runs only in native Linux operating systems. There is also a Virtual Machine (VM) with all dependents for non-Linux users. In this case, a VM software (e.g., VirtualBox, VMware) is required. UR encourages all of those who do not have access to a real robot arm to explore its products, including manuals, drawings, and software updates. Polyscope is the Graphical User Interface (GUI) programming environment. This powerful tool offers an intuitive robot user interface that can simulate three types of UR robots. Universal Robot UR3 (UR3), Universal Robot UR5 (UR5), and UR10, all named based on the payload supported.

Previous to simulate UR robots, it is necessary to initialize the robot and set up the virtual environment. For this purpose, the simulator accepts a script level to control the virtual robot arm. The Universal Robot Script (URScript) is the native programming language used to interact with the robot. Language includes numbers, variables, as well as flow control

statements. The specification for users is also included in the material provided by UR. An example of how to use URScript is founding in Listing 2.9.

```

1 Robot Program
2 Loop var_1?=False
3   var_1?=socket_open("10.1.1.214",30000)
4   Wait: 1.0
5   movej([1.545, -2.35, -1.31, -2.27, 3.358, -1.22], a=1.4, v=1)
6   var_6?=1.545
7   var_8?=1
8   Loop var_8?≠0
9     movej([var_6, -2.35, -1.31, -2.27, 3.358, -1.22], a=4, v=5)
10    joint_position?=get_actual_joint_positions()
11    socket_send_string(joint_position)
12    Wait: 0.01
13    var_7?=socket_read_ascii_float(1,timeout=0.003)
14    var_6?=var_6+0.01
15    If var_7[0]?=0
16      var_8?=1
17    Else
18      var_8?=var_7[1]

```

Listing 2.9: Example of a URScript.

It is also possible to establish a network connection with external devices. URSim offers diverse client interfaces that allow this interaction including [47, 48]:

- Socket Communication

Establishing communication with the robot using the Transfer Control Protocol (TCP)/ Internet Protocol (IP) protocol is possible. In this case, the robot works as a client and another device as a server/controller. Data can be transferred via TCP sockets using URScript commands to open and close sockets and send and receive messages from the server. Table 2.1 and Table 2.2 exemplify such principal information as defined by Universal Robots for controlling and monitoring the robot remotely. The data transmitted from each TCP socket could be different in detail from each other. The primary interface is used to transmit the robot’s state data and additional messages. The secondary interface only can be used to transmit the robot state data.

Table 2.1: Parameters of the primary interface defined by Universal Robots

Primary		
Port no.	30001	30011
Frequency [Hz]	10	10
Receive	URScript commands	URScript commands
Transmit	Robot state data	–
	Additional messages	–

- Real-time Interfaces

URSim is also able to use a real-time interface with a better update frequency rate than primary or second interfaces. The controller sends the robot state data and receives

Table 2.2: Parameters of the secondary interface defined by Universal Robots

Secondary		
Port no.	30002	30012
Frequency [Hz]	10	10
Receive	URScript commands	–
Transmit	Robot state data	–

URScript commands from the URSim. Table 2.3 shows the main differences in regard to ports and update rates concerning primary and secondary interfaces.

Table 2.3: Parameters of the primary interface defined by Universal Robots

Real-time		
Port no.	30003	30013
Frequency [Hz]	500	500
	125	125
Receive	URScript commands	–
Transmit	Robot state data	–

2.1.8 Universal Robot (UR10)

As mentioned above, URSim can represent UR3, UR5, and UR10 models; all of them are designed to let automate repetitive and well-defined tasks. Typically, the industrial processes (e.g., assembly, pick, and place) require more significant actions and heavier weight in laborious applications; in these cases, the UR10 model is ideal for automating these applications. The UR10 industrial robot arm has six joints, and each one can rotate $+360$, -360 degrees. Typically, UR10 has six DOF: base joint, shoulder joint, elbow joint, and three wrists joints (see Figure 2.9). Technical specifications related to UR10 are summarized in Table 2.4 and Table 2.5.

Figure 2.9: Universal Robot UR10. Source: Adapted from [49]

A set of move functions defines robot trajectories: joint space, linear, and circular blends (i.e., `movej`, `movel`, `movep`). Each movement command has a specific structure.

Table 2.4: Specification values defined by Universal Robots

Specification	
Payload	10 kg/22 lbs
Reach	1300 mm/51.2 in
Degrees of freedom	6 rotating joints
Programming	Polyscope graphical user interface

Table 2.5: Axis movements robot arm defined by Universal Robots

Movement		
Axis	Working range	Maximum speed
Base	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 120^\circ/Sec.$
Shoulder	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 120^\circ/Sec.$
Elbow	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 120^\circ/Sec.$
Wrist 1	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ/Sec.$
Wrist 2	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ/Sec.$
Wrist 3	$\pm 360^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ/Sec.$

1. **Movej**, makes linear movements that are calculated in the robot arm joint space.
2. **Movel**, makes linear movements that are calculated in the robot arm tool space.
3. **Movep**, makes blend circular movements that are calculated in the robot arm tool space.

Table 2.6 shows the parameters for **movej** functions and the units of measurement for some of the parameters.

Table 2.6: Movej Parameters

Parameters	
q:	joint positions
a:	joint acceleration of leading axis [$^\circ/s^2$]
v:	joint speed of leading axis [$^\circ/s$]
t:	time [s]
r:	blend radius [m]

An example of how to use **movej** message is found in Listing 2.10.

```

1  movej([Base, Shoulder, Elbow, Wrist1, Wrist2, Wrist3],
2  a=acceleration, v=speed)
3  movej([1.545, -2.35, -1.31, -2.27, 3.358, -1.22], a=4, v=5)

```

Listing 2.10: Example of a movej message.

2.1.9 Robot Controller

A robot controller is a logical place that allows establishing communication with the robot arm. To establish a connection with the robot, the controller can send commands and actions to the robot, e.g., stop messages. At the same time, it can receive data from the robot, e.g., the current position, through the bidirectional channel. There are two types of robot controllers:

a physical device or a script developed by software. A programmed script is advantageous to bring new possibilities to develop, edit, and create new functions to interact with the robot, and the commonly used languages are C ++, Java, and Python; however, Python is the selected language that presents more support [50].

2.2 Related Work

In this section, we move to explore the literature of related works of our research, aligning with both scenarios explored in this document. Firstly we address related works for Low-latency Edge Robot Control with P4 datapaths. Subsequently, we provide associated contributions for Programmable Edges for Data Center selection based on Flow RTT metrics. Relevant aspects of related works of each scenario are highlighted and summarized separately.

Gradually, the idea of infusing intelligence into the network comes turning a reality. New efforts to achieve a stateful network are focused on the data plane programmability, bringing in-network computing-based solution [51, 52]. In [41], is introduced the cloud offloading concept for different edge computing applications (e.g., smart home and city). In [53], it has been investigated as an in-network solution for low notification latency. Authors approached two methods to implement a content-based publish/subscribe system into the network layer, and they mainly differ by using different protocols (i.e., Openflow vs. P4). To accomplish this, they use an SDN controller to register the publisher and subscriber and learn notification sources located in the network to construct a delivery tree. The quired forwarding rules are installed on the switch by the controller and are applied based on a subscription match defined by the publisher. In both cases, results show the achievement of low latency delivering notifications.

In [54], authors explore how to implement security logic using programmable data plane devices. Thus, they use P4 language to implement a mechanism for time detection of Destributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks and achieve promissory results with more than 98% accuracy and latency of about 250 ms. In [55], an approach is presented based on the in-switch processing for DDoS attack detection. Monitoring functions are offloaded to the data plane using the OpenFlow protocol. René Glebke et al. [56] bring an implementation for computer vision functionality on a programmable network device, using the P4 programming language for defined match/action stages. The proposed system can identify interest patterns in the image data. The results and presented results expose the possibility of guiding a small autonomous car over different courses and taking up to 19 decisions per second.

Lately, collaborative robots in industrial scenarios have become more common. In [57], authors developed a setup to integrate robot arms and human collaboration. In this integration, they use the Digital Twin Digital Twin (DT) concept in the Fourth Industrial Revolution to demonstrate the impact of the delays caused by cloud platforms in Virtual Reality Virtual Reality (VR)/Augmented Reality Augmented Reality (AR) applications. In [45] explored the remote robotic control over long distances using the digital twins' framework. Authors investigate how to reduce the visual feedback delay and reaction times for unexpected changes in a particular application where a human operator controls the DT while the DT controls the remote robot. The distances evaluated between the operator and robot are higher than 100 km. Cloud computing initiative accepts programmable network devices, turning to one's advantage of offloading applications and computing them into the network.

Inside industrial networks, IoT is one of the most seductive topics these days. [58] is one interesting paper in this field that is toward low latency communication in a hardware implementation

of the IIoT environment. In this context, the authors highlight the massive amount of data produced by sensors in this kind of scenario, where often the data is used to enhance predictive maintenance through a machine learning process. However, handling a high amount of data can cause congestion in the IIoT network and hinder achieving very fast communication with data centers. To fill this gap, they define an original architecture communication, including a P4 switch. Thanks to the real implementation, the results obtained show an adequate performance in terms of network parameters for a real industrial environment. In [59] has been explored as an in-network solution for industrial controlling. The authors unified industrial machinery with the controlling process utilizing cloud environments. In that regard, they are inherently challenged by the delay and jitter of networking and controlling. To improve the control design, they applied an in-network control by offloading small but critical tasks into network elements in P4. The more relevant aspects of principal-related works mentioned above are summarized in Table 2.7.

Table 2.7: Related works list of different solutions regarding offloading computing

Reference	Project	In-network P4-based	Dataplane	Ultra Low Latency	Remarks
[53]	Content-based Publish/Subscribe in Software Defined Networks	Yes	BMv2	No	Application
[54]	Offloading Real-time DDoS Attack Detection to Programmable Data Planes	Yes	BMv2	No	Security
[55]	StateSec: Stateful Monitoring for DDoS Protection in Software Defined Networks	No	No	No	Security
[56]	Towards Executing Computer Vision Functionality on Programmable Network Devices	Yes	SmartNIC	No	Computer Vision
[57]	Towards Human-Robot Collaboration: An Industry 4.0 VR Platform with Clouds Under the Hood	No	No	Yes	Virtual Reality
[45]	Remote Robot Control with Human-in-the-Loop Over Long Distances using Digital Twins	No	No	Yes	Robotic Control
[58]	Achieving Low Latency Communications in Smart Industrial Networks with Programmable Data Planes	Yes	SmartNIC	Yes	IoT
[59]	Towards In-network Industrial Feedback Control	Yes	SmartNIC	Yes	Cloud
	This work	Yes	BMv2	Yes	Robotic Control

From the other angle, with the extensive applications migration to the cloud, cloud data centers are challenged to guarantee the quality of service and experience than ever before; they need to monitor performance in the network connections to diagnose problems timely. With the increase in the number of IoT devices, there has also been an increase in network traffic generated by these devices. Additionally, IoT devices can generate different types of traffic, such as voice, video, and data traffic, which may have different bandwidth and latency requirements. In the cloud, traffic can be generated by different types of services and applications. As applications become more complex and data-intensive, there is a growing demand for modern data centers to aim for very high throughput, ensure performance to achieve tasks quickly and efficiently, and offer low latency; even nowadays, new applications are designed with ultra-low latency in mind.

With the innovation evangelism of IoT, new challenges are appearing. IoT applications grow fast, and as a result, a significant amount of traffic is being transmitted in the network due to the constant stream of data. IoT application traffic can saturate the bandwidth on traditional network infrastructure and cause network congestion or impact the performance of other services or applications that share the same network resources. Particularly in scenarios where high-frequency data updates are required or real-time data processing and response times are crucial, the data center cloud needs to guarantee that its network infrastructure can provide connections to support these applications.

IoT applications generate vast amounts of data that need to be handled (e.g., transmitted, processed, and stored). Studies divulge that TCP traffic flow in some cloud data centers

surpasses 99% [60]. Depending on the application type, fast response times are expected for the application to function correctly; otherwise, any delay can have serious consequences. One main consideration to contribute to bridging the gap is to detect and prevent occurrences and ensure the performance and reliability of the network. To this end, some measurement techniques can be used in network monitoring to assist in reaching the early identification of patterns in the TCP flow traffic, such as RTT [61], a salient metric to understand network performance in terms of latency. Having a brief look at a TCP connection, the communication executes with the sender sending a segment, and the receiver responds with a second segment that carries a generated acknowledgment; at the beginning of this process, a timer is also initiated, the RTT is described as the time it takes to send a segment until it is acknowledged.

Nowadays, a perspective to offload applications into the network layer is more achievable. IoT is drawing significant attention, and papers for emerging IoT deployments are increasing, particularly for service-based solutions. In [62], authors are concerned about the traditional Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) architecture and its limitations, such as not allowing in-network functions for service enhancements, and how this can affect the progressive increase of IoT deployments. To this end, they introduce the programmable Bluetooth Low Energy Service Switch (BLESS) built on the software switch, PISCES [63], a transparent switch node between two communicating BLE devices. BLESS is an original BLE-based data plane boosted by P4 that allows in-network functions such as monitoring and control for IoT services enhancement by examining the packets at the service layer. At present, network measurement in programmable data planes is an exciting approach. Newly developed systems contribute to monitoring traffic flow performance to assist network operators in analyzing performance anomalies. Dapper [19] is a passive RTT monitoring system that helps to analyze TCP performance in the data plane. Dapper relies on the TCP protocol in cloud communications to diagnose limitations or a root cause of congestion by the sender, the network, or the receiver. Authors prototype the solutions in P4 to monitor TCP statistics directly in the data plane at line rate. Dapper presents some limitations, like just covering 15% occurrences of network events.

Another few new approaches continue on the same line as the early work to focus on measuring TCP performance in the data plane. In [16], X.Chen et al. introduced a passive algorithm running on the data plane to track bidirectional flows on a 10Gbps campus network traffic link. They gathered TCP data flows to extract the TCP timestamps from packets and measure the RTT. P4 boosted the implementation of the algorithm in a Barefore Tofino programmable switch. Results show impressive accuracy measurements of 99% using 4MB data plane memory. This approach can contribute to optimizing network performance. A network administrator can achieve much more accurate measurements and resolve to troubleshoot issues faster.

RTT is considered an important transport diagnostic that can help network operators to analyze network performance, especially in transport layer protocols such as TCP. Unusual RTT measures can indicate an uncommon performance in the network, such as congestion, delay, or packet loss also can indicate security anomalies such as routing attacks. In [64], S Sengupta et al. argue about P4RTT, a modern but challenging RTT measurement system to improve QoE monitoring. P4RTT is an in-network solution that aims for QoE monitoring deployed in the data plane of an on-path programmable switch in real-time. With this, authors point to enabling features such as the adaptability in the network through the data plane based on the solution on the RTT metric to estimate the QoE on end-users; however, many challenges are discussed in this work, including TCP retransmission of lost packets. Results indicate that the introduced system can collect at least 98% of RTT samples in a lengthy trace. Promissory benefits can be explored based on this work. Prior works inspired the development of a new

system that focuses on continuous RTT monitoring directly in the data plane, [65], Dart measures continuous RTT throughout the lifetime of a connection. The system is a prototype for the Tofino switch boosted with P4, experiment results were obtained with real campus traces, and results show 99% measured RTT samples. Authors consider Dart’s accuracy closely to the software tool tcptrace, even performing at line rate with long campus traces. The more relevant aspects of principal-related works mentioned above are summarized in Table 2.8.

Table 2.8: Related works list of different solutions regarding RTT computing

Reference	Project	In-network P4-based	Dataplane	Ultra Low Latency	Remarks
[62]	SDN-based Service Automation for IoT	Yes	PISCES	No	Programmable BLE service switch
[19]	Dapper: Data Plane Performance Diagnosis of TCP	Yes	Hardware Switch	Yes	Analyzes TCP Performance
[16]	Measuring TCP Round-Trip Time in the Data Plane	Yes	Tofino Switch	Yes	Passively and continuously RTT monitoring
[65]	Continuous In-Network Round-Trip Time Monitoring	Yes	Tofino Switch	Yes	Dart: RTT measurement system
	This work	Yes	BMv2	Yes	Reroute Traffic for Data Center Selection

2.3 Summary

This chapter introduced the background of the relevant literature by covering the main concepts that set up the context of this dissertation. We briefly introduced the main concepts that form an essential part of making progress on this dissertation, such as the narrating of SDN, and PDP, P4 defining the packets pipeline process; furthermore, programming and compiling a P4 target. We approached a hot topic area these days, such as industrial networks, to go deep into two different use cases. From an SDN perspective, we aim to improve application latency for industrial network scenarios. We leverage the programmable data plane and the P4 languages to introduce in-network solutions. In the coming chapters, we will cover the identified use cases in more detail.

Chapter 3

Low-latency Edge Robot Control with P4 datapaths

Industry 4.0 is a hot topic nowadays, emphasizing automating traditional robotic control supported by present-day paradigms. These days are more common than ever before to see collaborative robots in industrial systems. In these scenarios, it is a must to take quick action in case of unexpected situations appear. Advanced control and machine learning techniques supported new robust robot controllers with more intelligence to monitor the robot and react timely when needed. This chapter approaches an in-network solution to investigate downloading basic robotic control functions in a programmable data plane device. We use P4 to boost our solution. P4 can do basic tasks to parse and grab data to execute calculations (e.g., threshold, distance), craft a custom message, and send it back to the robot arm or robot controller.

The chapter is organized into distinct sections and subsections. Firstly, we present the research motivation by discussing traditional and current practices for robotic control, including the control messages. Secondly, we explain the problem definition. Then, lined up with the focus of this work, objectives are proposed based on the problems identified related to latency issues. In addition, we explain the methodology to achieve the objectives proposed. Consequently, we dive into the system overview to propose a low-latency edge robot control case. The system scenario investigated encloses a virtual robot arm, a P4 switch, and a robot controller. Initially, we examine the scenario without in-network control, and then we describe our in-network P4-based solution. Thirdly, system implementation and experimental evaluation are depicted; in this section, we expose the impact of delays in cloud-native-based solutions and how the delays affect end-users. Finally, we introduce our concluding remarks.

3.1 Motivation

Nowadays, advances in robotics have allowed robots to be more collaborative when carrying out specific tasks. These new robots have adopted the name of cobots [66] and have unique characteristics concerning their predecessors. Among them, we can mention:

- **Safer work environment:** Robots are designed with collaborative workplace involvement humans in mind. Since robots guarantee a safer work environment, they can be working next to an operator.
- **Do better than humans:** Can make well-defined tasks faster and more accurate than

human workers. Besides that, they can also calculate their trajectories from one point to another point.

- **External sensors:** They can have external sensors (e.g., camera, proximity sensor, acceleration sensor). Those sensors are used to detect unexpected obstacles or even humans. With this, robots can avoid possible **collisions**, **actuator damage** in the system, or even **human injuries**.
- **Powerful controller:** There is a direct link between a robot and a robot controller that enable communication. The controller is programmed to monitor the behavior of the robot steadily. Figure 3.1 illustrates a traditional robotic control.

Figure 3.1: Traditional robotic control.

With the arrival of new technologies, new trends have emerged. Cloud computing is an emerging trend in computing, which offers agility, elasticity, and practicality to perform complex tasks using remote servers. The evolution of SDN and NFV is aiding in promoting the cloud migration process. Many industries (e.g., transportation, shopping) contemplate the (public) cloud as the primary location for enterprises to store data and applications. Benefits such as reducing operational costs, scalability and agility, high availability, and flexible resource management have captivated businesses. Lately, new verticals, including industry 4.0, have been captivated by the cloud computing paradigm. This solution improves operational management, enabling robotic control by adding a direct link to an individual robot controller centralized or even offloaded to the cloud. However, with more applications moving to the cloud, new challenges appear. Today's network infrastructure needs to support cloudification adoption and treat challenges, like packet loss, congested links, and variations in delays, for new demands, especially for time-sensitive applications. Figure 3.2 depicts a representation of robotic control from the cloud. In this scenario, networking devices (e.g., router, switch) maintain communication between ends. Network uncertainty complications lie on the unreliable path to the cloud.

Figure 3.2: Centralized robotic control.

Notwithstanding, next-generation wireless systems (5G) offer improvements in network capacity and added ultra-low latency support. Still, wireless messages can be unsuitable for latency-critical applications such as robotic control due to the undeterministic stability of the wireless

connection (i.e., interference, backscattering, or even jamming) that disrupts information communication flow. Figure 3.3 depicts a high overview of traditional robotic control. The robot sends messages carrying on the current position to the network device, while the network device forwards the same messages to the centralized controller. The controller will also send a message back to the robot in case of any required action. In particular, if a message generated by the centralized controller to stop the robot's motion is affected by delays or even packet loss, there will be an error between the intended and real stop positions, potentially causing the severe hazards mentioned above.

Figure 3.3: Traffic congestion in robotic control.

On the other hand, recent advances in data plane programmability have fueled in-network solutions, opening new opportunities allowing simple computations to be offloaded to the network itself. In-network solutions' main advantage is the capability to execute some requests (i.e., tasks) wholly in the data plane, out of the centralized controller's reach. Due to the edge's physical proximity (much closer to the requester), we can overcome network uncertainty issues in the core and significantly reduce latency and reaction time. According to [67], in some data centers, more than 99% of the traffic measured for cloud computing service is TCP.

3.2 Problem Definition

The current limitations of robotic control functions in programmable devices are the following:

1. **Control messages:** The robot arm and the robotic controller can establish bidirectional communication to exchange packets using TCP sockets. However, it is necessary to investigate how the flow messages look to have some notions to craft a packed, the main parameters to consider (i.e., protocols used), and introduce a P4 router into the picture.
2. **P4 messages:** It is necessary to intercept, analyze, and manipulate the packets within TCP communication between URSim and the robot controller in the data plane. In this case, it is necessary to sync all the Acknowledgement (ACK) and Sequence (SEQ) numbers in every new message created in the P4 router.
3. **Performance evaluation:** An evaluation of the P4 router with the complete in-network process is indispensable. It has to maintain the full capabilities of the network. The network's throughput has not to be affected, independently of the in-network process; it has to conserve a high-reliability forwarding.

3.3 Objectives

The present section aims to deploy a robotic controlling function offloaded to the network using P4 as the programming languages' solution in the data plane to address the identified limitations.

To this end, the following objectives are proposed:

- **Design an P4-based in-network solution:** The advantage of this approach is P4 supports a line rate for packet processing and, at the same time, can deliver a low latency in the communication due to the proximity of the edge P4 router with the target.
- **Validation Environment:** It is achieved by setting up an experimental environment featuring a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) implementation of a virtual system using URSim as a represents for a real arm, a P4 router to forwarding, and generates packets and a python script as a controller to establish a TCP socket communication with the target (robot arm).
- **Maintain the TCP session:** One of the biggest challenges is properly maintaining the TCP session to guarantee a fully in-network solution. To handle the TCP synchronization problem can be taken strategies in the P4 program, such as defining a threshold position for the robot, and when a match with a restricted position occurs, the P4 router will notify the robot controller by sharing position message and also at the same time create a new stop message to stop the robot with valid ACK and SEQ numbers.
- **Evaluate the in-network solution:** It is necessary to analyze the in-network solution compared with a traditional solution to generate a robotic control action like the emergency stop and evaluate the performance of the control action in both scenarios.

3.4 Methodology

To achieve the objectives mentioned above are proposed the following activities:

- **Literature review:** It compels the study and analysis of the state of the art of in-network processing to be supported in robotic control. The study of robotic controlling functions and P4 language to be used for the In-network P4-based implementation. The review of the Universal Robotics Simulator and the physical robotic arm.
- **Testbed implementation:** After reviewing the literature, we move to the implementation of a testbed. As a first part of the process, identify the impact of an error (stop position difference) where the robot controller is much further from the robot. The device directly attached to the robot is a networking device.
- **Performance evaluation:** Firstly, We evaluate the traditional scenario, for an emergency stop, by sending the stop message from the controller running in the cloud; we mainly focus on how the latency on the link to the controller can affect the packet message and impact the time to stop the robot. Secondly, we evaluate our in-network P4-based approach. Here, the stop message is sent directly from the P4 device, avoiding the link to the controller.

Considering the previously mentioned antecedents, this chapter intends to introduce programmable dataplanes to explore and detect potential benefits concerning traditional industrial robot con-

trol via an in-network solution. Mainly, we present an in-network edge robot control application using programmable switches (i.e., offloaded to the programmable data plane) capable of acting in time (i.e., reply to the robot) to sudden changes in the workspace. To address our aim in our strategy, we leverage the capability of networking programmability. In our approach, We implement basic custom robotic control tasks to parse and analyze the TCP communication between the robot and the controller and perform in-network computation (e.g., distance, threshold). Notably, we analyze the messages' payload data (sent by the robot to the controller) to identify a position threshold violation in the programmable data plane. The network device will reply with generated custom messages (i.e., stop messages) to deliver that action to the robot arm within no time.

To do so, we created a testbed implementing a virtual scenario. We use URSim to simulate the robot arm, an appropriate tool to reproduce the kinematic of high DOF robotic arms. URSim uses a native programming language (i.e., URScript); therefore, using some metrics and parameters, we can control the movement of robots. Additionally, it can also communicate with external equipment by using TCP sockets. In the data plane, we prototype our solution using P4. One of the main advantages of P4 is to guarantee that the basic computation can perform in line rate (i.e., no overhead is introduced), an essential factor in delivering low latency replying with direct messages. We show that in our application, we can manipulate packets properly in the TCP session.

3.5 System Overview

This section aims to promote the capabilities of PDPs (e.g., P4 router) and investigate the impact of P4-based devices working near the industrial target components (e.g., robot arm, sensor) in a connection to a centralized server with non deterministic links. Concretely, in this case, we go a little deep in the direction of low latency requirements for critical actions (e.g., emergency stop, synchronization) when needed.

This proposal is intended to serve as a way to join PDPs and robotic control and open opportunities in emerging technologies, such as Industry 4.0. Firstly, we explain a traditional scenario without in-network control, subsequently, the same system with in-network P4-based implementation. We also present each part enclosed in the design.

3.5.1 Traditional scenario without in-network control

Accordingly, the system explored includes a robot arm and a robot controller. The software running on the robot arm provides instructions to perform repetitive tasks in the workplace. Instead, the controller is designed to take inputs and send outputs; it is in charge of performing verification, failure response, synchronization, etc.

Figure 3.4 presents a high-level overview of the system architecture and the experimental setup for a traditional scenario without in-network control. On the left-hand side, we are using URSim to represent the real UR10 robot arm. URSim is working as a client and executes the commands received from the controller. We also configured an initial start position, kinematic, and step size for its movements. Moreover, the robot sends messages containing its current position ❶ to the router. Right in the middle, for this case, we have a simple router. The router does forwarding the messages from the robot to the controller. On the right-hand side, we have the robot controller, a programmed script implemented in Python to set positions and actions in

Figure 3.4: Scenario without in-network control.

the robot. The controller also starts a TCP session with the robot for all the communication and analyzes all arriving messages afterward. Besides, the controller is configured to send a stop message ② to the router when an emergency stop is needed.

We detected that the network links present uncertain properties (i.e., delay, packet loss) that influence all packets messages coming from the controller to the router in this traditional scenario, and when the robot receives the stop message from the router, this messages already suffer network traffic effects and is not guarantee a stop position in time. Consequently, the robot receives the action message late, causing an error measured from the expected to the real stop position.

3.5.2 In-network P4-based implementation

In the traditional scenario, without in-network control, we detected a position stop error. We are conscious that this can evolve into a collision or further hazards. To mitigate it, we explored an in-network P4-based implementation.

Figure 3.5: In-network P4-based implementation.

Figure 3.5 shows an overview of the in-network P4-based system implementation and experimental setup. As in the previous system. On the left-hand side, the robot URSim works as a client and executes the commands received from the controller. The configuration for the kinematics, including acceleration, velocity, and step size of robot movements, is the same as the prior scenario. The robot also sends messages with its current position to the router ①.

On the right-hand side, we programmed a Python script to represent the robot controller's action (i.e., monitoring robot positions and emergency stops). It establishes a TCP com-

munication with the robot arm and waits for all incoming messages. The controller is also programmed with a threshold to detect violations in the joint base position; in the case of receiving a message breaking the threshold, it will send the necessary information to produce an emergency action (i.e., stop message) ②.

We implemented an in-network P4 solution using mininet, represented as the P4 router in the topology. To this end, we use the reference P4 software switch BMv2. When the robot sends a message with its current position, P4 device analyzes that message (parses + table matches) to identify that position. In case there is no threshold violation in the robot position, P4 device forwards the original messages to the controller. However, when P4 device detects a threshold violation in the robot position, it generates a new message containing the same action of the controller (i.e., stop messages) and sends it back directly to the robot ③. Now, P4 device becomes an edge robot controller capable of deciding how to route the traffic flows.

3.6 System Implementation

3.6.1 Preliminary Considerations

It is important to discuss two preliminary considerations to provide intelligence to a programmable device such as a P4 router and allow the total resolution of some tasks in the data plane, such as a request, without practically reaching the robot controller.

3.6.1.1 Avoiding the link to the controller

In the traditional scenario for the robotic control, we identified that the connection to the controller is exposed to suffer from delays that can directly affect the accuracy of the application needed of Ultra-low Latency Ultra-low Latency (ULL). We proposed an in-network P4-based implementation to offload robotic control functions directly in the programmable network device to fill this gap.

Figure 3.6: Avoiding the link to the controller.

Using an in-network P4-based application to control the robot as shown in Figure 3.6, it is necessary to introduce the P4 device, maintaining the TCP session between the robot and the robot controller. In case the P4 device needs to construct or manipulate any parameter from an incoming message, it is necessary to sync the ACK and SEQ numbers competently to maintain the TCP parameters valid for both borders.

As detailed in subsection 3.5.2, we focus our efforts on avoiding the link between the router and the controller. To this end, in our in-network scenario, when the robot shares ① the current

position with the robot controller, every message is analyzed by the P4 router to identify a match with the defined threshold saved on the payload `tcp_match_payload` of the P4 program.

In case this movement results in a match with the defined threshold, the P4 router will begin to act as the robot controller. It will create a reply with a new ACK and SEQ numbers to the robot and send the defined action ② (i.e., stop message) without notice to the real robot controller. If the robot controller does not receive any notification from the robot, the ACK and SEQ numbers will not be in sync, and the TCP connection will fail.

3.6.1.2 Switch-in-the-middle TCP handling

To solve the TCP session challenge presented above, we use an approach similar to TCP veto [68] (see Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: TCP session approach.

In Figure 3.5, when the robot shares the current position message ① and exists a match in the P4 router with the defined threshold, the P4 router will forward that messages to the robot controller and at the same time, it will be able to reply to the robot with a new message containing the stop action using valid ACK and SEQ numbers ③. Therefore, when the controller notes that it needs to send a stop-action ②, it will be rejected by the P4 device as a duplicate message, with synced ACK and SEQ numbers.

3.6.2 URSim Implementation

We implemented a script in the URScript (see Listing 3.1) to perform the robot actions, including specifying a starting position, velocity, acceleration, and step size for its movements. We configured the IP server address and port number. To define the robot trajectory movements, we used the joint position movement(`movej`); the structure of the position movement messages involves all six DOF as well as velocity and acceleration. For experimental purposes, we considered using the first DOF (base joint) of the UR10 as a reference. We also programmed the script to get the actual joint position and send it as a message position to the controller. To

Figure 3.8: In-network scenario.

obtain a gradual increase in the joint movement position, we added a step size value. Finally, the robot waits for an action from the controller; otherwise, it will continue with its trajectory.

```

1  Loop var_1?=False
2      var_1?=socket_open("10.1.1.214",30000)
3      Wait: 1.0
4      movej([1.545, -2.35, -1.31, -2.27, 3.358, -1.22], a=1.4, v=1)
5      var_6?=1.545
6      var_8?=1
7      Loop var_8?≠0
8          movej([var_6, -2.35, -1.31, -2.27, 3.358, -1.22], a=30, v=5)
9          joint_position?=get_actual_joint_positions()
10         socket_send_string(joint_position)
11         Wait: 0.01
12         var_7?=socket_read_ascii_float(1,timeout=0.003)
13         var_6?=var_6+0.1
14         If var_7[0]?=0
15             var_8?=1
16         Else
17             var_8?=var_7[1]

```

Listing 3.1: Robot Script.

3.6.3 P4 implementation

In the in-network implementation, we use P4 as a solution for the programming language to be implemented in the data plane. P4 gives us high-level abstractions and supports target-independent implementations. As mentioned before, basically, a P4 program has a parser, match + action tables, and a deparser. Inspired by the potential benefits identified in the previous work, we leverage the algorithm introduced in [69] to explore this use case. No relevant modifications were implemented on the original algorithm for our implementation; the complete code is also available in the annex B.

Inside the P4 code, we identify three key parts:

- **Robot header**

For the edge robot control application in P4, we use `movej` data structure (Listing 2.10)

to define a custom header (Listing 3.2) to identify all messages from the robot. We are considering the base position messages to match; this value is stored in the payload content (payload). In our implementation, we only consider 5 bytes of data.

```

1  header tcp_match {
2      bit<8> robot_msg;
3      bit<40> payload;
4      bit<240> payload_end;
5  }
```

Listing 3.2: Robot header.

- **Robot TCP match table**

The value stored in the payload is used to produce a match with a predefined threshold in the table.

```

1  table tcp_exact {
2      key = { hdr.tcp.payload : exact; }
3      actions = {tcp-payload-match ; NoAction;}}
```

Listing 3.3: Robot TCP match table

- **Robot action**

When a match occurs, the action is applied. The action involved generates a message with the necessary action data to send back to the robot and produce an emergency stop.

```

1  action tcp_payload_match(bit<8> robot_msg ,
2      bit<40> payload_match , bit<9> port) {
3      hdr.tcp_match.robot_msg = robot_msg; // (
4      hdr.tcp_match.payload = payload_match; // 0)
5      meta.modified = 0x1;
6      standard_metadata.egress_spec = port; }
```

Listing 3.4: Robot Action.

The match+action pipelines allow triggers for the detection of specific robot positions. To identify the message position from the robot in the P4 router, we follow the structure of the **movej** message introduced in Listing 2.10. In our implementation, the received position from the robot is shown in the Listing 3.5. We consider the base joint position to perform a match with the threshold, remarking that values in the pose can be positive and negative and have different sizes; in our test **2.063**.

```

1  movej ([2.063, -0.72, -1.57, -1.34, 3.214, -0.272])
```

Listing 3.5: Message position from the robot.

To perform the robot stop action, the robot will read a socket message (timeout 0.01). If no message arrives, the movement continues. We send a flag "(0)" to stop the robot. After parsing the message and extracting the payload (i.e., base joint position), the match+action pipeline starts. Figure 3.9 presents the P4 match+action table, representing the match payload (tcp_match.payload) extracted from (Listing 3.5) and take the defined action in (Listing 3.4), to stop the robot movement.

We describe the flow diagram of the P4 implementation, generated using P4 Graphs¹, for this end, flow diagrams are speared in two, the P4 ingress control pipeline and the parse.

¹<https://github.com/p4lang/p4-hlir/blob/master/bin/p4-graphs>

tcp_match_payload	Action	Data
2.063	tcp_payload_match	(0)

Figure 3.9: P4 table match parameter.

The ingress pipeline in Figure 3.10 shows the logic flow while parsing a packet. When a packet arrives, the first step is to parse the IPv4 header. If the etherType is IPv4, then the IP header is parsed. Figure 3.11 shows the parse graph. The P4 Parser will detect the different packet header sequences within packets, and header fields are extracted from the packet to perform the match + action functions.

Figure 3.10: P4 ingress pipeline.

3.6.4 Controller Implementation

To perform the robot controller actions, we implemented a script in Python. Listing 3.6 shows the controller script configuration. Initially, we configured the IP server address used by the robot and port number to establish the TCP socket communication. The controller is getting the position sent from the robot (`c.recv`); this position is compared with the defined threshold (`msg5`); in case to receive a higher value, it sends the action (`c.send`).

Figure 3.11: P4 parser.

```

1  HOST = "192.168.10.3"    # The remote host
2  PORT = 30000            # The same port as used by the server
3
4  count = 0
5  s = socket.socket(socket.AF_INET, socket.SOCK_STREAM)
6  s.setsockopt(socket.SOL_SOCKET, socket.SO_REUSEADDR, 1)
7
8
9  s.bind((HOST, PORT)) # Bind to the port
10 s.listen(5) # Now wait for client connection.
11
12 c, addr = s.accept()
13 print ("Starting RX")
14 print ("Delay ", delay)
15 val=0
16 val1=0
17 while (count < 1000):
18     try:
19         msg = c.recv(1024)
20         msg2 = msg.split(",")
21         msg3 = msg2[0].split("[")
22         msg4=list(msg3[1])
23         msg5=float(msg3[1])
24         val=val+1
25         if msg5 >= 1.88:
26             print(msg5)
27             print("-----YES-----")
28             time.sleep(delay)
29             c.send("(0)");
30             val1=1
31             if val1 == 1:
32                 print ("Pose Position = ", val ,msg)
33                 val1 = 0
34                 s.close()
35                 c.close()

```

```

36         #count = 1000
37
38     except socket.error as socketerror:
39         count = count + 1
40
41     s.close()
42     c.close()
43
44
45     print ("Program finish")

```

Listing 3.6: Controller Script.

3.7 Experimental Evaluation

This section aims to analyze our experimental evaluation’s performance, especially to evaluate the error for the stop position. This error is measured in terms of distance (i.e., millimeters) and is calculated as the difference between the robot’s expected and actual stop positions. Then, we describe our testbed configuration in the emulation setup subsection and explain the metrics used for the experiments, as well as an explanation step-by-step of the experimental procedure. Besides, in our evaluation, we consider the error for both scenarios, traditional robot control without in-network control and in-network robot control with P4, to plot and analyze them.

3.7.1 Emulation Setup

Our testbed is implemented using a Virtual Machine with 2048 MB running Lubuntu 16.04 in a virtual scenario. The topology is running using Mininet², a widely used emulator for SDN systems. It includes two hosts and a router. The first host (Robot) is running URSim v3.12.0 with a defined script (Listing 3.1) to send a message with its current position. The router runs the P4 program using BMv2. The second host (controller) executes a Python script (Listing 3.6) to start a TCP communication and process all incoming messages from the robot.

The robot arm is directly connected to the P4 router; for this experimental test, we assume that the robot controller can be at different distances from the robot. In the link between the P4 router and the robot controller, we use Linux Traffic control (tc)³ to represent different distances from where the controller can be located to send the messages and add the latency for the experiments. We also explore the impact of the error based on the kinematic configuration.

For our implementation, when the robot receives a stop message, we evaluate the position measured when the robot stops as much traditional control scenario as an in-network control scenario. We calculate the error by using the stop position of the robot, and we subtract the expected stop position from the actual stop position.

3.7.2 Performance Metrics and Workload

We consider different performance metrics for the experimental procedure in our experimental evaluation. In the controller, we thought of a range from 0 ms to 300 ms for the delays in the link between the router and the controller. In contrast, in the robot, we explored the kinematic,

²<http://mininet.org/>

³<http://man7.org/linux/man-pages/man8/tc.8.html>

we use acceleration movements with values of $30^\circ/s^2$, $80^\circ/s^2$, $130^\circ/s^2$. For its movement length, the robot uses a step size (0.1 mm, 1 mm). The robot is configured with the same start position and velocity used during every experiment evaluation. To this end, the controller can send a stop message to the robot when it violates a threshold position. This way, we evaluate the error behavior (i.e., variation of the expected robot stop position and actual robot stop position). To assess the results, we compare results obtained from both scenarios, which means when the stop message is generated in-network or in the traditional way (i.e., without in-network control).

The steps for the experimental procedure in the traditional robot control scenario without in-network control are described below:

- Step 1: Controller establishes a TCP communication to the robot and analyzes incoming messages afterward.
- Step 2: Robot sends its current position and reads any incoming message from the controller.
- Step 3: Controller analyzes all incoming messages to learn about the current robot position.
- Step 4: The robot is in motion, and the current position obeys a defined threshold.
- Step 5: Controller acknowledges to the robot about the current positions received and keeps on expecting to take any action.
- Step 6: The robot is in motion, and the current position reaches a defined threshold.
- Step 7: Robot controller receives the message that violates the threshold, then generates and sends a stop message to the robot.
- Step 8: Generated message from the robot controller passes through the link between the router and controller, and it suffers from a delay that highly affects the time of the action.
- Step 9: Robot executes the action received from the controller (i.e., stop order).
- Step 10: Rerun previous steps using the different values of the metrics mentioned above (step size, acceleration, and delay).

The steps for the experimental procedure in the in-network P4-based implementation are described below:

- Step 1: Controller establishes a TCP communication to the robot and analyzes incoming messages afterward.
- Step 2: Robot sends its current position and reads any incoming message from the controller.
- Step 3: P4 router forwards the messages to the controller and analyzes (parses + matches) specific payload data (current robot position) from the robot.
- Step 4: Controller analyzes all incoming messages to learn about the current robot position.
- Step 5: The robot is in motion, and the current position obeys a defined threshold.
- Step 6: Controller acknowledges to the robot about the current positions received and keeps on expecting to take any action.

- Step 7: P4 router forwards traffic in both directions, and the synchronization for both end-points is in line.
- Step 8: The robot is in motion, and the current position reaches a defined threshold.
- Step 9: P4 router matches the position of the target and takes the corresponding action. It creates a correct TCP segment (by calculating valid ACK and SEQ numbers) containing a reply message to the robot with a new payload to stop the robot's movement immediately.
- Step 10: At the same time, the P4 router forwards matched position message to the controller to avoid a TCP disconnection.
- Step 11: Robot controller receives the message that violates the threshold, then generates and sends a stop message to the robot.
- Step 12: Generated message from the robot controller passes through the link between the router and controller, and it suffers from a delay that highly affects the time of the action.
- Step 13: P4 router receives the stop message from the controller, but it is discarded as duplicates, with synced ACK and SEQ numbers.
- Step 14: Robot executes the action received from the P4 router (i.e., stop order).
- Step 15: Rerun previous steps using the different values of the metrics mentioned above (step side, acceleration, and delay).

3.7.3 Emulation Results

In this section, we present the experimental results comparing results from the traditional scenario for robotic control compared to the in-network scenario; in both cases, we evaluate the error in the position when the stop message is generated by the robot controller (scenario 3.4) compared to when the stop message to the robot is generated in the network (scenario 3.5). We evaluate the performance in terms of error (mm) by calculating the error as the difference between the threshold and the actual stop position.

We validate that the starting point of the error stop position is the link delay, as well as the kinematic configuration of the robot (e.g., acceleration, length movements) also contributes to increasing the impact on the error. The results in Figure 3.12 show the results of the experiments prior mentioned; we use a heatmap to represent the error measured in our color scale. The entries tending to a light green color correlate with higher errors that correspond to errors without in-network action. On the top, the entries for the delay of 0 ms (purple label) represent the results from the in-network action. We can mitigate this error by offloading the robot control action directly into the network using P4.

3.8 Concluding Remarks

3.8.1 Lessons learned

The error (stop position) behavior tends to increase when the delay increases from the robotic controller command. We are also considering if the robot controller running from different places (even the cloud) can cause so much latency. We demonstrated that it is possible to mitigate

Figure 3.12: Stop position error of the control action without in-network operation.

this error by sending messages directly from the P4 device. We are already investigating a use case with real networking devices and a real robot arm, expecting to delve deep into network control applications.

3.8.2 Limitations

It is important to judge the efficiency of our proof of concept using a real robot arm and a programmable dataplane device to have better notations of how the error impacts the performance or can cause an accident.

Some limitations of the initial implementation that can be considered include:

1. **Virtual Environment.** Currently, all the results were collected in a virtual environment. A real physical environment should be explored to understand better and validate our proof of concept.
2. **Real-time communication with the robot.** URSim also offers real-time communication to explore, enabling the real-time we will be capable of using a higher frequency to exchange messages between both end-points.
3. **Advanced position value matching with P4.** For this first implementation, we are considering just one joint value to detect incoming messages from the robot arm. It is common to have more than one movement in industry 4.0 applications. Hence, it is important to improve the filtering of messages by the P4 router.
4. **Additional robot control protocols.** To validate our proof of concept with other robots, it is necessary to consider what kind of protocols they use.

3.8.3 Conclusions

In our proof of concept prototype implementation, we demonstrated that some functions from a robot controller could be offloaded to a programmable data plane device using P4. Indeed, our experimental implementation using P4 addresses new opportunities and challenges to introduce programmable data planes in Industry 4.0 for robotic controlling.

We showed how the kinematic configuration of the robot (i.e., acceleration, step size) could affect an impact in error (stop position). We are also considering if the robot controller runs from different places (even the cloud) and can cause so much latency that it is not possible to react in time in a critical situation. We demonstrated that it is possible to mitigate this error by sending messages directly from the P4 device.

3.8.4 Future work

Considering a scenario with more than one robot (commonly in Industry 4.0) where robots work in a collaborative space in synchronization with higher possibilities of being in a collision course, robots can detect sudden changes in the operational area using joint sensors. Swift and precise interventions must avoid a collision with other robots or even with humans. This approach uses a programmable network device (e.g., a P4 router) to fill the gap.

Figure 3.13 describe a use case for future research where two robots are working nearby, Robot 1 ① and Robot 2 ② are sharing its current position through the network. Some basic control functions from the controller can be offloaded in the P4 device to perform actions and prevent

any possible collision in the collaborative workspace, crafting a message for anyone of Robots (2 or 4) and synchronizing the communication with the robot controller.

Figure 3.13: Multi-robot control system.

Chapter 4

Programmable Edges for Data center selection based on Flow RTT metrics

It is well-known that computer networks are growing faster than ever, transforming the traditional way people know them and pushing professionals to create a new mindset to learn about them. Nowadays, we are facing a new decade in computer networks. Rising paradigms are filling into position and are frequently considered more relevant and suitable for current and future data communications network applications. A present-day case of strategic alliances is the joining of the cloudification paradigm and collaborative robotics that are putting efforts into releasing the cloud robotics area. Formerly, robots lacked intelligence and were limited to perform not more than repetitive tasks/processes. A paradigm shift empowered a robotics revolution and allowed hundreds of robotic breakthroughs, including developing sophisticated appliances that enable communication with an appliance (e.g., controller, server) and receive information (i.e., instructions) to command the robot. Habitually, those communications are based on data network infrastructure. Today, it is more often that robots rely on the internet network, getting a much performance while executing tasks.

Network monitoring is based on approaches such as active and passive monitoring. Traditional measurement systems use different techniques to detect faults in computer networks. Active network monitoring produces additional traffic to sample its behavior. Passive network monitoring captures and analyzes traffic statistics at a specific point. Generally, techniques focus on measuring Synchronize (SYN)/ ACK packets; developed algorithms also consider RTT as a valid metric to validate the network performance and detect any issues.

This chapter introduces the second use case of this work. Firstly, we present the research motivation by discussing traditional and current practices for network monitoring. In addition, we introduce our approach to tracking abnormal traffic increases in cloud data centers by directly monitoring programmable data planes. Secondly, we depict the problem definition section that introduces some limitations in implementing the present use case, objectives that introduce our strategies to our aims, and methodology. We propose a methodology to achieve objectives based on the problems identified for edge application's latency. Besides the above, we cover the system overview, system implementation, and experimental evaluation. The system being investigated encloses a cloud data center and a core data center. Finally, we comment on the concluding remarks.

4.1 Motivation

Monitoring the cloud application traffic is a necessary approach to understanding the state of deployments for both providers and consumers. In terms of Quality of Service (QoS), QoE is essential to collect metrics and analyze their characteristics (e.g., RTT, inter arrival time, retransmission). Moreover, to prevent violations in the SLA of services offered through the cloud. There are various techniques for effective traffic monitoring, like active and passive monitoring approaches to measure network latency; both are widely accepted and work towards the same goal but with different methodologies. Active monitoring looks to find faults in the network state by injecting probe traffic into the network. Besides, it offers complete visibility into the network, turning easier to detect issues (e.g., packet loss, jitter) before they hit an end-user. In contrast to active monitoring, passive monitoring tracks real data, providing detailed information regarding the network's measured node. Some techniques often used involve capturing and analyzing the flow packets in a network. Information collected can indicate valuable insights (e.g., anomalies in network traffic, potential cyber attack) to help to minimize an indisposed performance of the network and consequently have a disgusting impact on the user experience.

Advances in network monitoring and programmable data planes have opened up new possibilities for developing and implementing new algorithms to run on programmable switches for various purposes, including making measurements passively at line rate. In this way, network operators can leverage opportunities to diagnose performance problems promptly. Recent research has proposed using passive monitoring algorithms running in P4 programmable switches to measure RTT metric. Measuring RTT at the data plane level can bring many opportunities and benefits. Among them, we can mention:

- **Performance:** Measuring RTT metric direct in the data plane for real-time routing changes. One of the more essential features of a programmable data plane is realizing a measure per packet of traffic. This is valuable in scenarios that need fast-moving rerouting to send traffic, like a congested link.
- **Security:** It is known that getting RTT values higher than usual while monitoring network latency can represent an attack (e.g., routing attack, IP spoofing). Tracking RTT metric on the flows can boost accuracy in detecting attacks.
- **Applications:** Previous research [70] showed the evaluating performance where the control plane and the data plane were working away from each other. Results revealed that RTT measured between both planes increases by more than the double delay. Moving computation to the data plane indeed represents an impact on the performance by reducing time computation.

Chapter 2 briefly introduced the cloudification concept and mentioned how approaches such as NFV are supporting virtualization technologies towards a network cloudification approach, highlighting the potential with which different end users can be benefited from on-demand network access that shares a pool of resources, including servers, storage, and applications. This tendency is widely known as cloud computing. Nevertheless, the prerequisite to providing access to computing services is network connectivity. Nowadays, in areas such as industrial networks and IIoT, robotics has become one of the main areas focused on leveraging and applying cloud capabilities, and most recently came up with the rise of an approach of cloud robotics (see figure 4.1). This trend is established on the concept of an internet shared among robots, ideally collecting and providing a shared database by offloading resources from data center servers to user equipment.

Figure 4.1: Conventional robotic scenario.

Commonly, cloud data centers are robust in storage and processors and use networking appliances (e.g., routers, switches) to handle remote communications with a piece of user equipment (e.g., a robot). For example, figure 4.2 illustrated a representation of an overview of how cloud robotic communication works. The link between the two peers enables sending and receiving messages directly to each other; the connection might be direct or indirect and depends on the data center location; in the case of an indirect link, the network appliance act as a router. To forward messages between peers, first, on the left winger, user equipment (represented by a robot arm) sends the robot message to the robot controller running in the cloud server; the message might be a request to access specific information stored in the cloud data center. Then, on the right winger, large data centers (i.e., a cloud) usually collect, process, and store a large volume of data of robots in real-time, control the robots remotely, and monitor their performance. Connecting robots to the cloud fills the need for more processing power and storage capacity on the robot itself. By offloading some of the processing and analysis to the cloud, results are more feasible to process the large amounts of data generated by robots and even improve the overall performance of the robot by using machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms. Finally, the robot controller in the data center attends to the request from the robot and replies with another message giving the requested subject.

Figure 4.2: Elementary cloud robotic communication.

Emerging trends such as edge computing have opened opportunities to move the computation power offered by data centers close to the end user. A reduced location mainly characterizes these edge data centers and a small infrastructure with limited storage, power, and processing characteristics. Figure 4.3 shows a cloud robotic scenario employing a link connection with an edge data center (①). Engaging an edge data center offers the possibility of processing the data closer to the end user; this is suitable for reducing latency and furnishing an improved experience for customers. Besides improved performance processing data on edge, an edge data center also reduces operational costs compared to other alternatives (e.g., core data center) that require network features (e.g., bandwidth, high storage) pretty expensive.

On the other hand, as illustrated in Figure 4.4, a cloud robotic scenario can also operate with

Figure 4.3: Scenario employing an edge data center.

a link connection with core data centers (②). Moreover, as the network scale expands, users' requirements are increasing sprightly in terms of bandwidth and reliability of the network. From there, a core data center should be suitable for improving link reliability. Nearly all of these data centers utilize enormous infrastructure to provide and distribute cloud computing services compared with an edge data center.

Figure 4.4: Scenario employing a core data center.

In both previous scenarios, improving service processing capabilities and ensuring high service reliability demands significant efforts. In addition, maintaining the network's performance requires a suitable procedure to detect performance or even security issues in time. Indeed, these risks become more outstanding when a cloud data center provides applications to remote users' equipment with added connections where latency can appear, causing a sudden slowdown and generating drawbacks. A widely-known metric used to measure latency performance in networks is RTT. RTT is the metric to measure the time takes for packets to go from point A

to point B and back again to the initial position. High statistics of RTT values can indicate an anomaly in the network, such as congestion.

Recently, programmable data planes of programmable switches have boosted network traffic monitoring mainly due to flexible parsing and registers capabilities. In addition, due to the high-speed packet processing capabilities of a programmable data plane is possible to detect anomalies quicker. Emerging programming languages allow the execution of algorithms in the data plane, between them, P4 language. P4 supports the flexibility to develop programs able to respond to new circumstances in the network timely, including monitoring latency to track RTT statistics and detecting problems directly in the data plane. In line with that, and aiming to avoid congestion for time-sensitive applications, we propose to explore and approach to track TCP RTT flows between an end user and an edge and core data center directly in a programmable data plane. The measured RTT values can indicate the performance and responsiveness of running applications and be an indicator of traffic congestion on the links. In order to avoid congestion and keep a low latency available path, corrective actions can be taken in the data plane, such as providing fast rerouting for network traffic.

4.2 Problem Definition

The current limitations of programmable edges for data center selection are the following:

1. **Control traffic:** An application communication in a data center can suffer variations in latency based on where it is running (i.e., edge or core). For latency-sensitive robotic applications, continuous low latency is critical to function correctly. To this end, it is necessary to determine a suitable way to maintain the best available path to send traffic.
2. **P4 implementation:** To guarantee the available link with minor latency, it is necessary to conduct continuous traffic monitoring. Packets need to be analyzed as they flow through the network. Analyzing packet timestamps can indicate the RTT metric in order to identify the link exhibiting minor latency.
3. **Performance evaluation:** An evaluation of the P4 router to monitor the links and indicate the best path to send traffic is necessary. Even with an increase of RTT in the traffic flow, it is required to maintain the network's full capabilities.

4.3 Objectives

The present section aims to define the guidelines for deploying a data center selection application based on the RTT metric using the flexibility of a programmable data plane and P4.

To this end, the following objectives are proposed:

- **Design a P4-based in-network solution:** We consider the P4 device as a message router for selecting links of data centers. For the criteria to follow the appropriate link, we evaluate TCP traffic connections and analyze the RTT of flows to evidence network anomalies that can influence the performance of data center links.
- **Tracking RTT metrics:** To track RTT metrics during a TCP session is necessary to track and match outgoing TCP packets with their acknowledgments and allow the resolution of some tasks in the data plane, such as setting a threshold in the P4 router to forward traffic onto a better route when higher RTT values than the threshold is detected.

In this way, it is possible to route traffic to a data center with the most optimal path at that point in time.

- **Validation Environment:** To validate our proof-of-concept implementation, we consider a virtual scenario. The topology is implemented on Mininet, considering a user-equipment as the TCP client, a P4 router as a programmable device next to the client (i.e., user equipment), and two links from the P4 router to forward the traffic. Besides, each one of these links is connected to a different host that represents the edge and core data center (i.e., TCP servers).
- **Evaluate the in-network solution:** Evaluating the in-network solution to validate the switching action in the links based on the RTT values for both data centers is necessary.

4.4 Methodology

To achieve the objectives mentioned above are proposed the following activities:

- **Literature review:** It addresses the exploration, study, and analysis of TCP RTT measurement in the data plane. The study of performance monitoring on programmable switches and P4 language algorithms to be used for the logical P4-based implementation. Moreover, the review of network traffic in cloudification and representative scenarios such as cloud robotics.
- **Testbed implementation:** For this, we emulate our implementation to recognize the network behavior (i.e., RTT metric) in a TCP socket session between two hosts that also present delays in links. We evaluate the conduct of the network for different timestamps when traffic tends to increase.
- **Performance evaluation:** We analyze the RTT in the P4 router. High values of this metric could mean congestion in the link. Our approach is based on a programmable P4 device to forward the traffic to another route to avoid congestion.

4.5 System Overview

This section approaches a study of classical network features, such as network monitoring and load balancing network for traffic in data center networks, from a new perspective by using the capabilities of a programmable data plane. In figure 4.5, we present a data center selection scenario using programmable data planes. Previously has been mentioned the chance of implementing corrective actions directly in the data plane by using P4. One of the recurring problems faced by network operators is congestion presented in network-limited connections. Accordingly, we investigate the prospect of improving applications latency during a TCP connection between end-user equipment and an edge or a core data center by using a P4 switch to forwarding the traffic flow suitably to select the appropriate data center link.

Fundamentally, as approached in the chapter above, in the robot control application. In this second use case, we keep the same track toward latency improvements to detect new action strategies. The new proposal intends to monitor TCP network traffic in a programmable switch (i.e., P4 router). This approach analyzes the RTT metric for the TCP packets surfing from end to end of a TCP client/server connection. We can track RTT directly in the data plane by supporting us with a programmable data plane (e.g., BMv2) and P4. The P4 router can

Figure 4.5: Programmable edges for data center selection.

track RTT metric of the packets during a TCP connection between the client (e.g., robot) and server (e.g., edge data center, core data center). In addition, the P4 router can apply corrective actions if higher RTT values are detected. For instance, act as a message router to turn traffic off in a different route (see routes (①) and (②) in figure 4.5). This significant action can contribute to avoiding anomalies (e.g., delay, jitter, packet loss) typically detected on the links. We shall explain the use case and regarded scenarios where the P4 router could act as a message router in the coming subsections.

4.5.1 Shifting from the Core to the Edge

Owing to the extended utilities a core data center can offer, many customers around the globe across different industry verticals are betting on this solution and have decided to host their applications on this vast infrastructure. However, it is not good enough to allocate all the resources in one unique place (e.g., core data center). There are different appreciable reasons to motivate a shift from the core and hold resources in another data center, like a power outage or a natural disaster that would decrease the availability of services for the end-user. Besides, with the appearance of new technologies, the ascension of new users is also increasing, and ever-growing workloads from new users are fast than ever before. Running applications, content to store, or data to analyze can produce those workloads. It does not even look attractive in terms of finances due to those workloads running up can represent a high cost for customers. On the other hand, implementing a second giant data center involve expensive duplicate hardware.

As a result, providers had to look elsewhere for data computing needs. Edge computing is empowering this shift due to the proximity factor. One of the major factors is how close the customer base is to the data center. Customers can run their applications out of their region, but the time it takes for the data to be sent or latency generated is considered. As illustrated in figure 4.6 we represent the scenario where the P4 router could balance the traffic and shift the flows from the core to an edge to handle a new communication between the user equipment and an edge data center. This scenario suits customers who want high-availability service and allocate applications closer to the end-user to accelerate communication and get faster deliv-

ery, such as applications in the financial and healthcare field, where delays or unavailability of services, even during short periods, can directly impact the performance of services or applications. In addition, operative costs can be more attractive when using an edge data center; hence service providers can also reduce the cost to customers.

Figure 4.6: Shifting from the Core to the Edge.

4.5.2 Shifting from the Edge to the Core

The popularity of edge computing has been coming up since a time ago, and many companies have decided to migrate their services or applications closer to the location where its needed, which is commonly known as the edge. Edge computing aims to treat identified challenges of core data centers, especially performing data processing and analyzing data much closer to where it originated. This approach has several benefits, including lower latency for services and applications that demands real-time interactions. However, specific scenarios with services and applications may require extensive, robust computing capabilities due to their resource-intensive and complex nature, such as industrial automation, autonomous vehicles, virtual reality, and augmented reality. In that cases, especially during peak hours when the workload increases, rapid elasticity, and scalability are required to allow resource-intensive tasks effectively. Services and applications may prefer to rely on a core data center that can quickly furnish more resources. In figure 4.7, we illustrate a second scenario where the P4 router could act as a message router, redirecting the traffic flows from an edge data center to a core data center in order to keep services or applications performing as expected from end-users.

Figure 4.7: Shifting from the Edge to the Core.

4.6 System Implementation

4.6.1 Preliminary Considerations

It is essential to mention some considerations regarding the second use case system implementation to provide intelligence to a programmable device such as a P4 router and allow the total resolution of some tasks in the data plane, such as a request to route traffic based on RTT metric.

4.6.1.1 Single TCP client to connect to multiple TCP servers

In multiple TCP connections is more common that one server performs duties simultaneously to many clients. In our approach, we must manage multiple connections to different servers from the same client. Figure 4.8 is an illustration of our topology. H1 represents a user-equipment and also represents the client in our TCP session. H2 and H3 represent the edge data center and core data center, respectively, and both are the servers to establish the TCP session. Aligned with the requirement to keep feasible communications between H1 and H2 or H3 to route messages and send traffic to the best path whether interface (i.g., ① or interface ②). The client must handle scenarios where a server becomes unavailable or unresponsive due to a disconnection in the TCP. The P4 device has the function of parsing incoming or outgoing TCP packets. It identifies the lesser link (with H2 and H3) that presents a lesser RTT to keep sending packets. However, after establishing a new TCP connection between H1 and any of

the servers, the session with the other server is disconnected.

Figure 4.8: Topology used for experimental evaluation.

4.6.1.2 Offline approach

We are considering only one TCP session between a client and one server to generate network traffic and measure the RTT of that traffic in the data plane. To this end, we use `iperf3`¹ as a traffic generator source. Then, H2/H3 executes the `iperf` server-side, whereas H1 runs the `iperf` client-side. Figure 4.9 represents the setup for our offline approach. In this case, the P4 program calculates RTT values sequentially, and we saved measurement values into a pcap collected in H1. However, this is a limitation in the use case for full validation.

Figure 4.9: Offline Approach.

4.6.2 P4 implementation

In the previous section was introduced the concept of the P4 router as a router message. Firstly, we focus on analyzing the traffic flows directly in the programmable switch. Besides, we also need to consider that the traffic implicated in the edge data center and core data center is TCP. To this end, in our implementation, we explore the benefits of the approach to the passive algorithm for measuring round trip time on the data plane. Inspired by the potential

¹<https://iperf.fr/iperf-download.php>

benefits identified in the previous work, we leverage the algorithm introduced in [71] to explore this use case.

The P4 program receives mirrored bi-directional traffic and can distinguish whether the current packet is a data packet or ACK response using the packet size as a reference. No output will be given when the P4 program gets a data packet. If the packet matched a previous ACK packet record, the algorithm successfully produced an RTT sample. RTT samples contemplate the network status condition between two end hosts. To measure RTT, no relevant modifications were implemented on the original algorithm for our implementation; the complete code is also available in annex C.

Inside the P4 code, we identify some major parts shown below:

- **RTT registers**

The algorithm uses array registers to store timestamps. The array holds current RTT values in the order shown below.

```

1  register<bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) rtt;
2  register<bit<32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) register_indices_of_rtt;
3  register<bit<32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) src_ips_of_rtt;
4  register<bit<32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) dst_ips_of_rtt;
5  register<bit<16>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) src_ports_of_rtt;
6  register<bit<16>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) dst_ports_of_rtt;
7  register<bit<32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) seq_nos_of_rtt;
8  register<bit<32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) ack_nos_of_rtt;

```

Listing 4.1: Registers.

- **Writing RTTs**

RTT samples are written in the payload section of the output report.

```

1  current_rtt_index.read(rtt_index, 0);
2  rtt.write(rtt_index, rtt);
3  register_indices_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, meta.hash_key + offset);
4  src_ips_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.ipv4.srcAddr);
5  dst_ips_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.ipv4.dstAddr);
6  src_ports_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.srcPort);
7  dst_ports_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.dstPort);
8  seq_nos_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.seqNo);
9  ack_nos_of_rtt.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.ackNo);
10 current_rtt_index.write(0, (rtt_index + 1) % MAX_NUMRTTS);

```

Listing 4.2: Writing RTT on registers.

- **RTT Action**

When the incoming ACK packet arrives, the algorithm fetches the entry and calculates the time difference.

```

1  bit<32> offset = 32w0;
2  timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key + offset);
3  if (outgoing_timestamp != 0) {
4      time_diff0 = standard_metadata.ingress_global_timestamp -
      outgoing_timestamp;
5  }

```

Listing 4.3: Calculating RTT value.

4.7 Experimental Evaluation

This section aims to evaluate the performance of the proposed research. Initially, the section describes the emulation setup for the experiments. Subsequently, the performance metrics for emulations are detailed. Last and not least, a detailed discussion of the results obtained from the experiments.

4.7.1 Emulation Setup

We implemented a testbed with an emulation setup running on the SDN emulator, Mininet, by using the June 2018 P4 BMv2 ². A virtual machine with the operating system Ubuntu 64-bit, base memory 2048 MB, and two processors. In figure 4.10 is illustrated the testbed used for the experimental evaluation in Mininet. We use Linux Traffic control (tc) to represent delay variations on the links (①) and (②) that remain due to the distances on the data centers.

Figure 4.10: Emulation setup.

4.7.2 Performance Metrics

As a starting point in the implementation, we use the iperf3 tool to send the TCP flows from the client (i.e., H1) through the link H1-S1 to the server (i.e., H2/H3) through the links S1-H2 or S1-H3. The P4 device measures the RTT values of that traffic. To visualize collected values, we use our offline approach. The traffic is sent from H1 to H2 and H1 to H3. In H1, we collect and save the traffic as a PCAP file. The links S1-H2 and S1-H3 include delay variations due to the distance between the edge and core data centers from the user equipment. For the experimental evaluation, we consider the delay variations on the links to the data centers. For the first experiment, we set the S1-H2 link to 2 ms and the S1-H3 link to 20 ms. In this experiment, the TCP traffic is sent during different periods of time (1,3,6,9, 12 seconds). For the second experiment, we modify the time (1s, 25s, 50s, 75s, 100s) and delay conditions. The delay in the S1-H2 link is set up to 50 ms, and the S1-H3 link to 100 ms. In both cases, the delays are implemented on Mininet.

²<https://p4.org/events/2018-06-06-p4-developer-day/>

4.7.3 Emulation Results

This section presents experimental results considering the scenario described in Figure 4.10. We send TCP traffic from H1 to H2 and H3 to represent the network’s traffic. We are also exploring the impact of RTT measurements when the network presents variations on the links. For this purpose, we represent network delays using Linux Traffic Control (tc). Table 4.1 presents the average for the RTT values calculated in different time intervals in the PCAP file collected in H1 during the first experiment. These values were collected under different delay conditions on the sessions between H1-H2 and H1-H3.

Table 4.1: RTT measured values for H1-H2 and H1-H3 during the first experiment

TCP Session	Link Delay (ms)	RTT (ms)
H1-H2	2	4.01
H1-H3	20	40.3
H1-H2	50	101.6
H1-H3	100	203.3

4.8 Concluding Remarks

4.8.1 Lessons Learned

Using the collected pcaps, we analyze the RTT values from TCP traffic between H1 and H2/H3, considering the different link conditions (delay) for H2 and H3 to represent latency between an edge and a core data center. The traffic collected on H1 suffers in performance under different link conditions. RTT values tend to increase as expected when the delay increases. High RTT values can indicate the link that is suffering from more delay or latency due to heavy traffic, the physical distance between the source and destination in the communication, packet loss, and retransmissions.

4.8.2 Limitations

Our approach explores the possibility of measuring the RTT on the TCP traffic for different sessions. This approach measures the RTT directly in the data plane. It leverages these RTT measurements on links to use them as the indicator to reroute traffic, prioritizing the path with less delay or latency to send the traffic. This use case is an initial approach to monitoring the traffic directly in the data plane and taking corrective actions in the environment of an industrial network such as a cloud robotic.

We explore data center selection links based on the RTT metric. Currently, we are able to analyze network performance, i.e., RTT in the TCP packets, and identify the performance on links. However, various limitations are faced during the implementation, including:

1. **Tracking the RTTs in real-time.** The evaluation uses the iperf tool to generate the TCP traffic in this approach. The traffic is collected and saved in a pcap used by the P4 program as an input to calculate the RTT. It is necessary to explore an approach with an evaluation of traffic in real time.
2. **Data center selection in real-time.** For this first implementation, we are assessing in an offline mode. The data center selection needs to occur based on the RTT flows of

real-time communication for testing and validation.

3. **Robot Control Application.** We discuss this use case considering a nonspecific robot control application. However, depending on the type of application, new aspects need to be considered, such as using a protocol optimized for low-latency communication.

4.8.3 Conclusions

This chapter presented a use case for tracking the TCP RTT metric at programmable edges for data center selection. RTT is a key metric for proper network monitoring that provides insights into network performance and can contribute to network troubleshooting of potential issues, such as bottlenecks in a specific connection. With this in mind, based on the RTT measurements for cloud applications, we address the solution to take corrective actions in time.

4.8.4 Future Work

To make feasible the Programmable Edges for Data center selection based on FLOW RTT metrics and obtain more meaningful empirical QoE performance study over TCP or other protocols, as future work, we plan a full integration on our approach considering the Tofino programmable switch and the CoppeliaSim³, a complete platform for robot simulators, widely used by educational institutions for its versatility for multi-robot applications.

Additionally, robots rely on the cloud in cloud robotics to accomplish their tasks. Basic and delicate applications like sensor data streaming, audio, or video depend on real-time communication. To this end, we also consider exploring the Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP), a protocol optimized for low-latency communication in a real-time client-server session.

³<https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/>

Chapter 5

Conclusions

This thesis presented circumstances that many applications can suffer in terms of performance with migration to a cloud environment, particularly two use cases in the industrial network area. This thesis provided an empirical robotic control application study and monitoring and tracking network traffic. In the following, we concisely summarize the contributions to reflect this thesis's goal and objectives.

5.1 Robot Control at Programmable Edges

Chapter 3 introduced the use case entitled Low-latency Edge Robot Control with P4 data paths. We designed and evaluated an in-network P4-based implementation to enable robotic control from the network's edge. Since a typical connection of a robot to the controller is exposed to external network factors (e.g., delay), it can be worst based on how distance the controller is. Low-latency applications are not unguarded to suffer from network factors, and the probability of inappropriate behavior on these applications increases. Our approach played a role in application latency improvement for the end-point (i.e., robot) without requiring direct cooperation by the robot controller. We stated all the reasonable steps to design an in-network offloaded logic capable of analyzing the information transmitted from the target and taking actions (i.e., generation of new messages, updating the message data, definition of thresholds). We conducted an extensive experiment using a fully reproducible emulation-based testbed.

The proposed in-network design demonstrated the potential to handle essential robot actions (i.e., emergency stop command) and avoid a link connection to the robot controller that can suffer through network traffic issues and harm the application behavior. Appropriately, the system being investigated encloses a robot and a controller that establish communication through a TCP session. Using the in-network design, one limitation is when the robot and the controller ACK and SEQ numbers are not synchronized, causing a TCP disconnection. In the in-network P4-based design, the P4 generates direct replies (i.e., stop message) to the target (i.e., robot) without interaction with the controller. However, at the same time, this also causes non-synchronization of all TCP parameters (e.g., ACK, SEQ) for both the robot and controller. One approach to avoiding a TCP disconnection is continuously forwarding the robot position messages to the controller. When the P4 threshold matches the robot's undue position message, it creates a new message to reply to the robot. When the controller learns about the robot's undue position, it sends the stop message, but this message is considered duplicated by the P4 and discarded it.

As far as we are aware, our approach is the first in-network robotic control application. Accordingly, with the results launched in the experimental evaluation when not using in-network applications, the error (stop position difference) increases depending on the delay of the controller command. Meanwhile, the results from the in-network approach indicate that this error can be drastically reduced or mitigated it. Indeed, we expect new opportunities for different ranges of applications and use cases can arise from here.

5.2 Tracking TCP RTT Metric at Programmable Edges

Chapter 4 introduced the use case entitled Programmable Edges for Data center selection based on Flow RTT metrics. We started up the design in-network P4-based solution for data center selection considering the performance of network connections. Since cloud robotics applications depend on low-latency links, it is necessary to offer connection availability to stay working as expected. In cloud network environments, it is common that traffic flows through unknown links due to the nature of cloud infrastructure. In addition, changes in the links on cloud networks can be frequent, occasioning more challenging to know the entire network path that traffic takes. It is required to have better control to get more visibility into the network flow due to, for a cloud robotic scenario, degraded communications between robots and the cloud infrastructure can significantly represent an important impact on the performance of the applications; latency or packet loss can contribute to occurs congestion in these communications.

We approached a flow analysis of traffic patterns to deal with traffic flows through unknown links and congestion scenarios. By understanding the flow patterns, strategies can be implemented to optimize the routing paths. To this end, network monitoring techniques may contribute to gaining insights into the traffic. RTT is a metric widely used for low-latency applications that asses an efficient network performance or congestion in network connections. Network congestion can be recognized with high RTT values. In our approach, in the topology proposed, we tracked the RTT metric for TCP traffic for the links.

However, one limitation is we evaluate the scenario considering an offline approach to analyzing the TCP traffic in PCAP format instead of in real-time. A lesson learned is the need for a single TCP client to connect to multiple TCP servers. One perspective to provide continuous connectivity and service availability is considering in our implementation preserving the state of the last TCP connection to be resumed on another endpoint (e.g., server). However, many requirements should be considered to be implemented on the P4 to handle checkpoints and restore TCP sessions, such as saving the complete state of the TCP sessions (e.g., SEQ numbers, ACK numbers, window size, checksum, and other relevant information). However, restoring a TCP connection cannot be commonly implemented; transferring the saved state to another endpoint can be tricky.

To summarize, we measure the RTT in the P4 device. To visualize and analyzes that values, we follow an offline approach to collect the flows into packet captures (PCAP). The early results, as expected, show that RTT values tend to increase when the delay on the links also increases, which is an indicator of latency on the link. For our approach, we look for intelligence to distribute traffic based on RTT values; however, to be a full solution, a real-time implementation is required for a better understanding. This is still an initial approach, and limitations need to be covered.

Bibliography

- [1] U. Dombrowski and T. Wagner, “Mental strain as field of action in the 4th industrial revolution,” *Procedia Cirp*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 100–105, 2014.
- [2] Y. Lu, “Industry 4.0: A survey on technologies, applications and open research issues,” *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, vol. 6, pp. 1–10, 2017.
- [3] W. McDonough, M. Braungart *et al.*, “The next industrial revolution,” in *Sustainable Solutions*. Routledge, 2017, pp. 139–150.
- [4] L. Thames and D. Schaefer, “Software-defined cloud manufacturing for industry 4.0,” *Procedia cirp*, vol. 52, pp. 12–17, 2016.
- [5] M. Vagaš, M. Hajduk, J. Semjon, L. Koukolová, and R. Jánoš, “The view to the current state of robotics,” in *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 463. Trans Tech Publ, 2012, pp. 1711–1714.
- [6] F. Semeraro, A. Griffiths, and A. Cangelosi, “Human–robot collaboration and machine learning: A systematic review of recent research,” *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 79, p. 102432, 2023.
- [7] C. Baroglio, A. Giordana, R. Piola, M. Kaiser, and M. Nuttin, “Learning controllers for industrial robots,” *Machine learning*, vol. 23, no. 2-3, pp. 221–249, 1996.
- [8] B. Galloway and G. P. Hancke, “Introduction to industrial control networks,” *IEEE Communications surveys & tutorials*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 860–880, 2012.
- [9] A. Nasrallah, A. S. Thyagaturu, Z. Alharbi, C. Wang, X. Shao, M. Reisslein, and H. ElBakoury, “Ultra-low latency (ull) networks: The ieee tsn and ietf detnet standards and related 5g ull research,” *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 88–145, 2018.
- [10] D. Kreutz, F. M. Ramos, P. E. Verissimo, C. E. Rothenberg, S. Azodolmolky, and S. Uhlig, “Software-defined networking: A comprehensive survey,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 103, no. 1, pp. 14–76, 2014.
- [11] N. G. Nayak, F. Dürr, and K. Rothermel, “Software-defined environment for reconfigurable manufacturing systems,” in *2015 5th International Conference on the Internet of Things (IOT)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 122–129.
- [12] D. Hancock and J. Van der Merwe, “Hyper4: Using p4 to virtualize the programmable data plane,” in *Proceedings of the 12th International on Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies*, 2016, pp. 35–49.
- [13] K. Zhou, T. Liu, and L. Zhou, “Industry 4.0: Towards future industrial opportunities and challenges,” in *2015 12th International conference on fuzzy systems and knowledge discovery (FSKD)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 2147–2152.

- [14] P. Bosshart, D. Daly, G. Gibb, M. Izzard, N. McKeown, J. Rexford, C. Schlesinger, D. Talayco, A. Vahdat, G. Varghese, and D. Walker, “P4: Programming protocol-independent packet processors,” *SIGCOMM Comput. Commun. Rev.*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 87–95, Jul. 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2656877.2656890>
- [15] F. Rodriguez, C. E. Rothenberg, and G. Pongrácz, “In-network p4-based low latency robot arm control,” in *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on emerging Networking Experiments and Technologies*, 2019, pp. 59–61.
- [16] X. Chen, H. Kim, J. M. Aman, W. Chang, M. Lee, and J. Rexford, “Measuring tcp round-trip time in the data plane,” in *Proceedings of the Workshop on Secure Programmable Network Infrastructure*, 2020, pp. 35–41.
- [17] N. Feamster, J. Rexford, and E. Zegura, “The road to sdn: an intellectual history of programmable networks,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 87–98, 2014.
- [18] E. Kaljic, A. Maric, P. Njemcevic, and M. Hadzialic, “A survey on data plane flexibility and programmability in software-defined networking,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 47 804–47 840, 2019.
- [19] M. Ghasemi, T. Benson, and J. Rexford, “Dapper: Data plane performance diagnosis of tcp,” in *Proceedings of the Symposium on SDN Research*, 2017, pp. 61–74.
- [20] A. Nordrum, K. Clark *et al.*, “Everything you need to know about 5g,” *IEEE Spectrum*, vol. 27, 2017.
- [21] R. Bifulco and G. Rétvári, “A survey on the programmable data plane: Abstractions, architectures, and open problems,” in *2018 IEEE 19th International Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HPSR)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [22] X. Zhang, L. Cui, K. Wei, F. P. Tso, Y. Ji, and W. Jia, “A survey on stateful data plane in software defined networks,” *Computer Networks*, p. 107597, 2020.
- [23] S. M. Mousavi and M. St-Hilaire, “Early detection of ddos attacks against sdn controllers,” in *2015 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 77–81.
- [24] C. Sun, J. Bi, H. Chen, H. Hu, Z. Zheng, S. Zhu, and C. Wu, “Sdpa: Toward a stateful data plane in software-defined networking,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 3294–3308, 2017.
- [25] V. Gurevich, “P4 tutorial,” <https://p4.org/assets/Nov-2015-P4-Bootcamp-P4-Tutorial.pdf>, November 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://p4.org/assets/Nov-2015-P4-Bootcamp-P4-Tutorial.pdf>
- [26] B. Tofino, “World’s fastest p4-programmable ethernet switch asics,” 2018.
- [27] T. Lévai, G. Pongrácz, P. Megyesi, P. Vörös, S. Laki, F. Németh, and G. Rétvári, “The price for programmability in the software data plane: The vendor perspective,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 2621–2630, 2018.
- [28] N. McKeown, *Programming the Forwarding Plane*, 2016, <https://stanford.io/3l6Lgh8>.
- [29] P. Bosshart, D. Daly, G. Gibb, M. Izzard, N. McKeown, J. Rexford, C. Schlesinger, D. Talayco, A. Vahdat, G. Varghese *et al.*, “P4: Programming protocol-independent packet processors,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 87–95, 2014.
- [30] P. L. Consortium, “P4 language,” 2016, <https://p4.org/>.

- [31] —, *The P4 Language Specification*, 2014, <https://p4.org/p4-spec/p4-14/v1.0.5/tex/p4.pdf>.
- [32] —, *The P4 Language Specification*, 2014, <https://p4.org/p4-spec/docs/P4-16-v1.2.1.html>.
- [33] N. McKeown, T. Anderson, H. Balakrishnan, G. Parulkar, L. Peterson, J. Rexford, S. Shenker, and J. Turner, “Openflow: enabling innovation in campus networks,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 69–74, 2008.
- [34] M. Shahbaz, S. Choi, B. Pfaff, C. Kim, N. Feamster, N. McKeown, and J. Rexford, “Pisces: A programmable, protocol-independent software switch,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, August 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://dl.acm.org/authorize?N19297>
- [35] H. Stubbe, “P4 compiler & interpreter: A survey,” *Future Internet (FI) and Innovative Internet Technologies and Mobile Communication (IITM)*, vol. 47, 2017.
- [36] S. Lee, K. Levanti, and H. S. Kim, “Network monitoring: Present and future,” *Computer Networks*, vol. 65, pp. 84–98, 2014.
- [37] A. Atary and A. Bremner-Barr, “Efficient round-trip time monitoring in openflow networks,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2016-The 35th Annual IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–9.
- [38] J. G. Herrera and J. F. Botero, “Resource allocation in nfv: A comprehensive survey,” *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 518–532, 2016.
- [39] R. Cziva, S. Jouet, and D. P. Pezaros, “Gnfc: Towards network function cloudification,” in *2015 IEEE conference on network function virtualization and software defined network (NFV-SDN)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 142–148.
- [40] M. Armbrust, A. Fox, R. Griffith, A. D. Joseph, R. Katz, A. Konwinski, G. Lee, D. Patterson, A. Rabkin, I. Stoica *et al.*, “A view of cloud computing,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 50–58, 2010.
- [41] W. Shi, J. Cao, Q. Zhang, Y. Li, and L. Xu, “Edge computing: Vision and challenges,” *IEEE internet of things journal*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 637–646, 2016.
- [42] M. D. Assunção, R. N. Calheiros, S. Bianchi, M. A. Netto, and R. Buyya, “Big data computing and clouds: Trends and future directions,” *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, vol. 79, pp. 3–15, 2015.
- [43] A. Sunyaev, “Cloud computing,” in *Internet Computing*. Springer, 2020, pp. 195–236.
- [44] B. Kehoe, S. Patil, P. Abbeel, and K. Goldberg, “A survey of research on cloud robotics and automation,” *IEEE Transactions on automation science and engineering*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 398–409, 2015.
- [45] I. A. Tsokalo, D. Kuss, I. Kharabet, F. H. Fitzek, and M. Reisslein, “Remote robot control with human-in-the-loop over long distances using digital twins,” in *2019 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [46] U. Robot, *Universal Robots Support*, 2014, <https://www.universal-robots.com/download/>.
- [47] U. R. Support, “Overview of client interfaces,” <https://www.universal-robots.com/how-tos-and-faqs/how-to/ur-how-tos/overview-of-client-interfaces-21744/>, November 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://bit.ly/2qNQFmw>

- [48] U. Robots, “Remote control via tcp/ip,” <https://www.universal-robots.com/how-tos-and-faqs/how-to/ur-how-tos/remote-control-via-tcpip-16496/>, November 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://bit.ly/2RG1BzV>
- [49] Wiredworks, “Meet universal robot ur10,” 2016, <https://wiredworkers.io/universal-robots-ur10/>.
- [50] Zacobria, “Universal robots,” 2015, <https://www.universal-robots.com/download/?option=18940>.
- [51] A. Sivaraman, A. Cheung, M. Budiu, C. Kim, M. Alizadeh, H. Balakrishnan, G. Varghese, N. McKeown, and S. Licking, “Packet transactions: High-level programming for line-rate switches,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGCOMM Conference*, 2016, pp. 15–28.
- [52] A. Sapio, I. Abdelaziz, A. Aldilajjan, M. Canini, and P. Kalnis, “In-network computation is a dumb idea whose time has come,” in *Proceedings of the 16th ACM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*, 2017, pp. 150–156.
- [53] H. Parzyjegl, C. Wernecke, and G. Mühl, “Content-based publish/subscribe in software-defined networks,” 2020.
- [54] Â. C. Lapolli, J. A. Marques, and L. P. Gaspar, “Offloading real-time ddos attack detection to programmable data planes,” in *2019 IFIP/IEEE Symposium on Integrated Network and Service Management (IM)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 19–27.
- [55] J. Boite, P.-A. Nardin, F. Rebecchi, M. Bouet, and V. Conan, “Statesec: Stateful monitoring for ddos protection in software defined networks,” in *2017 IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–9.
- [56] R. Glebke, J. Krude, I. Kunze, J. Ruth, F. Senger, and K. Wehrle, “Towards executing computer vision functionality on programmable network devices,” in *Proceedings of the 1st ACM CoNEXT Workshop on Emerging in-Network Computing Paradigms*, 2019, pp. 15–20.
- [57] B. G. Nagy, J. Doka, S. Racz, G. Szabo, I. Pelle, J. Czentye, L. Toka, and B. Sonkoly, “Towards human-robot collaboration: An industry 4.0 vr platform with clouds under the hood,” in *2019 IEEE 27th International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–2.
- [58] A. Atutxa, D. Franco, J. Sasiain, J. Astorga, and E. Jacob, “Achieving low latency communications in smart industrial networks with programmable data planes,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 15, p. 5199, 2021.
- [59] J. Ruth, R. Glebke, K. Wehrle, V. Causevic, and S. Hirche, “Towards in-network industrial feedback control,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 Morning Workshop on In-Network Computing*, 2018, pp. 14–19.
- [60] S. Bensley, L. Eggert, D. Thaler, P. Balasubramanian, and G. Judd, “Datacenter tcp (dctcp): Tcp congestion control for datacenters,” *RFC8257, Oct*, vol. 10, 2017.
- [61] J. Aikat, J. Kaur, F. D. Smith, and K. Jeffay, “Variability in tcp round-trip times,” in *Proceedings of the 3rd ACM SIGCOMM conference on Internet measurement*, 2003, pp. 279–284.
- [62] M. Uddin, S. Mukherjee, H. Chang, and T. V. Lakshman, “Sdn-based service automation for iot,” in *2017 IEEE 25th International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP)*, 2017, pp. 1–10.
- [63] M. Shahbaz, S. Choi, B. Pfaff, C. Kim, N. Feamster, N. McKeown, and J. Rexford, “Pisces: A programmable, protocol-independent software switch,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGCOMM Conference*, 2016, pp. 525–538.

- [64] S. Sengupta, H. Kim, and J. Rexford, “Fine-grained rtt monitoring inside the network,” *Measuring Network Quality for End-Users*, 2021.
- [65] —, “Continuous in-network round-trip time monitoring,” in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2022 Conference*, 2022, pp. 473–485.
- [66] M. Peshkin and J. E. Colgate, “Cobots,” *Industrial Robot: An International Journal*, 1999.
- [67] M. Alizadeh, A. Greenberg, D. A. Maltz, J. Padhye, P. Patel, B. Prabhakar, S. Sengupta, and M. Sridharan, “Data center tcp (dctcp),” in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM 2010 conference*, 2010, pp. 63–74.
- [68] T. John and E. Barry, “Tcp veto: A novel network attack and its application to scada protocols,” *Innovative Smart Grid Technologies (ISGT), IEEE PES*, 2013.
- [69] F. E. R. Cesen, L. Csikor, C. Recalde, C. E. Rothenberg, and G. Pongrácz, “Towards low latency industrial robot control in programmable data planes,” in *2020 6th IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 165–169.
- [70] H. D. Vu and J. But, “How rtt between the control and data plane on a sdn network impacts on the perceived performance,” in *2015 International Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference (ITNAC)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 179–184.
- [71] X. Chen, H. Kim, J. M. Aman, W. Chang, M. Lee, and J. Rexford, “Measuring tcp round-trip time in the data plane,” *ACM SIGCOMM 2020 Workshop on Secure Programmable Network Infrastructure (SPIN 2020)*, 2020.

Appendix A

Publications

- F. R. Cesen, L. Csikor, **C. R. R. Vitonera**, C. E. Rothenberg, and G. Pongrácz. Towards Low Latency Industrial Robot Control in Programmable Data Planes. In: *6th IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 165-169, Virtual Conference, June 2020.

Appendix B

Edge Robot Control

B.1 P4 Robot Code

```
1  \footnotesize
2
3  #include <core.p4>
4  #include <v1model.p4>
5
6  const bit<16> TYPE_IPV4 = 0x800;
7  const bit<8> UDP_TYPE = 0x11;
8  const bit<8> TCP_TYPE = 0x06;
9
10 //LEN variables
11 const bit<16> IPV4_LEN_d = 20;
12 const bit<16> IPV4_LEN = 16w20;
13 const bit<32> TCP_val_d = 32;
14 const bit<32> TCP_IP = 52;
15
16 //FIN LEN variables
17
18
19 const bit<16> IPV4_LEN_mod = 56;           // with DATA = 4
20 const bit<32> IPV4_LEN_mod_2 = 56;       // with DATA = 4
```

```

21 //const bit<16> IPV4_LEN_mod = 81;           // with DATA = 29
22 //const bit<32> IPV4_LEN_mod_2 = 81;        // with DATA = 29
23
24 //const bit<32> TCP_DATALEN = 0;
25 const bit<16> payload_LEN_mod = 16w56;      // with DATA = 4
26 //const bit<16> payload_LEN_mod = 16w113;   // with DATA = 29
27 const bit<16> IPV4_LEN_mod_check = 16w36;   // with DATA = 4
28 //const bit<16> IPV4_LEN_mod_check = 16w61; // with DATA = 29
29 //const bit<4> TCP_LEN_modl;
30
31 /******
32 ***** H E A D E R S *****
33 *****/
34
35 typedef bit<9> egressSpec_t;
36 typedef bit<48> macAddr_t;
37 typedef bit<32> ip4Addr_t;
38 typedef bit<8> payload_table_start_t;
39 typedef bit<40> payload_table_match_t;
40 typedef bit<440> payload_pose;
41
42 header ethernet_t {
43     macAddr_t dstAddr;
44     macAddr_t srcAddr;
45     bit<16> etherType;
46 }
47
48 header ipv4_t {
49     bit<4> version;
50     bit<4> ihl;
51     bit<8> diffserv;
52     bit<16> totalLen;
53     bit<16> identification;
54     bit<3> flags;
55     bit<13> fragOffset;

```

```
56     bit <8>    ttl ;
57     bit <8>    protocol ;
58     bit <16>   hdrChecksum ;
59     ip4Addr_t  srcAddr ;
60     ip4Addr_t  dstAddr ;
61 }
62
63 header udp_t
64 {
65     bit <16>  srcPort ;
66     bit <16>  dstPort ;
67     bit <16>  len ;
68     bit <16>  checksum ;
69     //payload – we only consider 5 bytes of data
70     bit <40>  payload ;
71 }
72
73 header tcp_t {
74     bit <16>  srcPort ;
75     bit <16>  dstPort ;
76     bit <32>  seqNo ;
77     bit <32>  ackNo ;
78     bit <4>   dataOffset ;
79     bit <3>   res ;
80     bit <3>   flags_1 ;
81     bit <3>   flags_2 ;
82     bit <3>   flags_3 ;
83     bit <16>  window ;
84     bit <16>  checksum ;
85     bit <16>  urgentPtr ;
86     bit <96>  options ;
87     //bit <40>  payload ;
88 }
89
90
```

```
91 header tcp_payload_t {
92     bit<8> payload_start;
93     bit<40> payload_match;
94     //bit<272> payload_end;
95 }
96
97 header tcp_payload_2_t {
98     //bit<8> payload_start;
99     //bit<40> payload_match;
100    bit<272> payload;
101 }
102
103 header tcp_payload_mod_t {
104     bit<24> payload;
105     //payload_pose payload;
106 }
107
108 header tcp_payload_mod_long_t {
109     bit<256> payload;
110     //payload_pose payload;
111 }
112
113 struct meta_tcp_t {
114     bit<16> srcPort;
115     bit<16> dstPort;
116     bit<32> seqNo;
117     bit<32> ackNo;
118     bit<4> dataOffset;
119     bit<3> res;
120     bit<3> flags_1;
121     bit<3> flags_2;
122     bit<3> flags_3;
123     bit<16> window;
124     bit<16> checksum;
125     bit<16> urgentPtr;
```

```

126     bit <96> options;
127 }
128
129 struct meta_ipv4_t {
130     bit <4>    version;
131     bit <4>    ihl;
132     bit <8>    diffserv;
133     bit <16>   totalLen;
134     bit <16>   identification;
135     bit <3>    flags;
136     bit <13>   fragOffset;
137     bit <8>    ttl;
138     bit <8>    protocol;
139     bit <16>   hdrChecksum;
140     ip4Addr_t srcAddr;
141     ip4Addr_t dstAddr;
142 }
143
144 struct tcp_metadata_t {
145     bit <16> full_length; //ipv4.totalLen - 20
146     bit <16> full_length_in_bytes;
147     bit <16> header_length;
148     bit <16> header_length_in_bytes;
149     bit <16> payload_length;
150     bit <16> payload_length_in_bytes;
151     bit <16> tcp_header_length_for_checksum;
152     bit <16> tcp_payload_pose; //p[
153     bit <64> tcp_payload_X; //X pose e.g., 0.720471
154     bit <32> TCP_DATA_LEN;
155     bit <32> IP_DATA_LEN;
156 }
157
158 struct tcp_metadata_mod_t {
159     bit <16> full_length; //ipv4.totalLen - 20
160     bit <16> full_length_in_bytes;

```

```

161     bit <16> full_length_in_bytes_mod ;
162     bit <16> header_length ;
163     bit <16> header_length_in_bytes ;
164     bit <16> payload_length ;
165     bit <16> payload_length_in_bytes ;
166     bit <16> payload_length_in_bytes_2 ;
167     bit <16> tcp_header_length_for_checksum ;
168 }
169
170 struct metadata {
171     /* empty */
172     bit <8>     modified ;
173     bit <32>    udp_payload_beginning ;
174     tcp_metadata_t tcp_metadata ;
175     tcp_metadata_mod_t tcp_metadata_mod ;
176     meta_tcp_t     meta_tcp ;
177     meta_ipv4_t    meta_ipv4 ;
178 }
179
180 struct headers {
181     ethernet_t     ethernet ;
182     ethernet_t     ethernet_copy ;
183     ipv4_t         ipv4 ;
184     ipv4_t         ipv4_copy ;
185     udp_t          udp ;
186     tcp_t          tcp ;
187     tcp_t          tcp_copy ;
188     tcp_payload_t  tcp_payload ;
189     tcp_payload_mod_t tcp_payload_mod ;
190     tcp_payload_2_t tcp_payload_2 ;
191     tcp_payload_mod_long_t tcp_payload_mod_long ;
192 }
193
194 /******
195 ***** P A R S E R *****

```

```
196 *****/
197
198 parser MyParser(packet_in packet,
199                 out headers hdr,
200                 inout metadata meta,
201                 inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {
202
203     state start {
204         transition parse_ethernet;
205     }
206
207     state parse_ethernet {
208         packet.extract(hdr.ethernet);
209         transition select(hdr.ethernet.etherType) {
210             TYPE_IPV4: parse_ipv4;
211             default: accept;
212         }
213     }
214
215     state parse_ipv4 {
216         packet.extract(hdr.ipv4);
217         transition select(hdr.ipv4.protocol) {
218             UDP.TYPE : parse_udp;
219             TCP.TYPE : parse_tcp;
220             default : accept;
221         }
222     }
223
224     state parse_udp {
225         packet.extract(hdr.udp);
226         //meta.udp_payload_beginning = hdr.udp.payload[127:96];
227         transition accept;
228
229     }
230
```

```

231     state parse_tcp {
232         packet.extract(hdr.tcp);
233
234         //FOR TCP
235         meta.tcp_metadata.full_length = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen - IPV4.LEN) * 8;
236         meta.tcp_metadata.header_length = (((bit <16>)hdr.tcp.dataOffset) <<
237     5);
238         meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length = meta.tcp_metadata.full_length -
239     meta.tcp_metadata.header_length;
240         meta.tcp_metadata.full_length_in_bytes = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen -
241     IPV4.LEN);
242         meta.tcp_metadata.header_length_in_bytes = (bit <16>)hdr.tcp.
243     dataOffset << 2;
244         meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length_in_bytes = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen -
245     IPV4.LEN) - ((bit <16>)hdr.tcp.dataOffset << 2);
246         meta.tcp_metadata.tcp_header_length_for_checksum = meta.tcp_metadata.
247     header_length_in_bytes + meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length_in_bytes;
248         meta.tcp_metadata.TCP_DATA_LEN = (((bit <32>)meta.tcp_metadata.
249     full_length_in_bytes)) - TCP_IP;
250
251         //testing
252
253         //meta.tcp_metadata_mod.full_length_in_bytes_mod = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen
254     - payload_LEN_mod);
255         //meta.tcp_metadata_mod.full_length_in_bytes = (meta.
256     tcp_metadata_mod.full_length_in_bytes_mod - IPV4.LEN);
257         //meta.tcp_metadata_mod.header_length_in_bytes = (bit <16>)hdr.tcp.
258     dataOffset << 2;
259         //meta.tcp_metadata_mod.payload_length_in_bytes = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen
260     - IPV4.LEN) - ((bit <16>)hdr.tcp.dataOffset << 2);
261
262         //meta.tcp_metadata_mod.tcp_header_length_for_checksum =
263     payload_LEN_mod;

```

```

254
255     //
256
257     //meta.tcp_metadata.tcp_payload_pose = hdr.tcp_payload.payload
[455:440];
258     //meta.tcp_metadata.tcp_payload_X = hdr.tcp_payload.payload[295:232];
259
260
261 //     meta.tcp_metadata.full_length_in_bytes = hdr.ipv4.totalLen - (((
bit <16>)hdr.ipv4.ihl) << 2); //(hdr.ipv4.totalLen - IPV4.LEN);
262 //     meta.tcp_metadata.header_length_in_bytes = (bit <16>)hdr.tcp.
dataOffset << 2;
263     // meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length_in_bytes = (hdr.ipv4.totalLen -
IPV4.LEN) - ((bit <16>)hdr.tcp.dataOffset << 2);
264     // meta.tcp_metadata.tcp_header_length_for_checksum = meta.
tcp_metadata.header_length_in_bytes + meta.tcp_metadata.
payload_length_in_bytes;
265     transition parse_tcp_payload;
266
267 }
268
269 state parse_tcp_payload {
270     packet.extract(hdr.tcp_payload);
271     transition parse_tcp_payload_2;
272
273 }
274
275 state parse_tcp_payload_2 {
276     packet.extract(hdr.tcp_payload_2);
277     transition accept;
278
279 }
280
281
282

```

```

283 }
284
285 /*****
286 ***** CHECKSUM VERIFICATION *****
287 *****/
288
289 control MyVerifyChecksum(inout headers hdr, inout metadata meta) {
290     apply { }
291 }
292
293 extern Register<T> {
294     Register(bit<32> size);
295     T read(bit<32> index);
296     void write(bit<32> index, T value);
297 }
298
299 /*****
300 ***** INGRESS PROCESSING *****
301 *****/
302
303 control MyIngress(inout headers hdr,
304                  inout metadata meta,
305                  inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {
306     action drop() {
307         mark_to_drop();
308     }
309
310     action ipv4_forward(macAddr_t dstAddr, egressSpec_t port) {
311         clone3(CloneType.I2E, 0, { });
312         standard_metadata.egress_spec = port;
313         hdr.ethernet.srcAddr = hdr.ethernet.dstAddr;
314         hdr.ethernet.dstAddr = dstAddr;
315         hdr.ipv4.ttl = hdr.ipv4.ttl - 1;
316         hdr.ipv4.identification = 0;
317

```

```
318     }
319
320     table ipv4_lpm {
321         key = {
322             hdr.ipv4.dstAddr: lpm;
323         }
324         actions = {
325             ipv4_forward;
326             drop;
327             NoAction;
328         }
329         size = 1024;
330         default_action = drop();
331     }
332
333
334     //UDP
335
336     action udp_forward_hack() {
337         hdr.udp.payload = 0x736963630a; // payload='sicc'
338         //hdr.udp.payload[127:96] = 0x73696363; // payload='sicc' + rest of
the payload
339         meta.modified = 0x1;
340
341     }
342
343     table udp_exact {
344         key = {
345             hdr.udp.payload : exact; //match just cica
346             //matching on substring is not really liked by the P4 compiler
347             //meta.udp_payload_beginning: exact; // match the cica at the,
and later add the rest of the payload
348         }
349
350         actions = {
```

```

351         udp_forward_hack;
352         NoAction;
353     }
354
355     default_action = NoAction;
356
357     const entries = {
358         0x636963610a : udp_forward_hack(); // match for cica
359         //0x63696361 : udp_forward_hack(); // match for cica +++++
360     }
361 }
362
363
364 //TCP
365
366 action tcp_forward_hack(payload_table_start_t payload_start,
payload_table_match_t payload_match, bit<9> port) {
367     //hdr.tcp_payload.payload = payload; // payload='s['
368     //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.payload = payload;
369     //hdr.tcp_payload.payload = payload; // payload='sicc'
370     //hdr.tcp_payload.payload = 0x736963630a; // payload='sicc'
371     //hdr.udp.payload[127:96] = 0x73696363; // payload='sicc' + rest of
the payload
372
373
374     //hdr.tcp.dataOffset = TCP_LEN_mod;
375
376
377     //Add new payload
378
379     //Removing the old headers
380     hdr.ethernet.setInvalid();
381     hdr.ipv4.setInvalid();
382     hdr.tcp.setInvalid();
383     //hdr.tcp_payload.setInvalid();

```

```

384     //hdr.tcp_payload_2.setInvalid();
385
386     //Updating ethernet
387     hdr.ethernet_copy.setValid();
388     hdr.ethernet_copy.dstAddr = hdr.ethernet.srcAddr;           //
Updated with srcaddr
389     hdr.ethernet_copy.srcAddr = hdr.ethernet.dstAddr;         //
Updated with dstaddr
390     hdr.ethernet_copy.etherType = hdr.ethernet.etherType;
391
392     //Updating IPv4
393     hdr.ipv4_copy.setValid();
394     hdr.ipv4_copy.version = hdr.ipv4.version;
395     hdr.ipv4_copy.ihl = hdr.ipv4.ihl;
396     hdr.ipv4_copy.diffserv = hdr.ipv4.diffserv;
397     //hdr.ipv4_copy.totalLen = IPV4.LEN_mod;                   //
New IPv4 len
398     hdr.ipv4_copy.totalLen = hdr.ipv4.totalLen;
// New IPv4 len for gen size
399     hdr.ipv4_copy.identification = hdr.ipv4.identification;   // Can
be set as 0
400     hdr.ipv4_copy.flags = hdr.ipv4.flags;
401     hdr.ipv4_copy.fragOffset = hdr.ipv4.fragOffset;
402     hdr.ipv4_copy.ttl = hdr.ipv4.ttl+1;
403     hdr.ipv4_copy.protocol = hdr.ipv4.protocol;
404     hdr.ipv4_copy.hdrChecksum = hdr.ipv4.hdrChecksum;        //
Will be recalculated
405     hdr.ipv4_copy.srcAddr = hdr.ipv4.dstAddr;                 //
Updated with dstaddr
406     hdr.ipv4_copy.dstAddr = hdr.ipv4.srcAddr;                 //
Updated with srcaddr
407
408     //Updating TCP
409     hdr.tcp_copy.setValid();
410     hdr.tcp_copy.srcPort = hdr.tcp.dstPort;                   //

```

```

Updated with dstPort
411     hdr.tcp_copy.dstPort = hdr.tcp.srcPort;           //
Updated with srcPort
412     hdr.tcp_copy.seqNo = hdr.tcp.ackNo;             //
Updated with ACK Robot-Controller
413     hdr.tcp_copy.ackNo = hdr.tcp.seqNo + meta.tcp_metadata.TCP_DATALEN;
        // Updated with SEQ (ROBOT-CONTROLLER) + TCP_DATALEN (
IPv4_TOTAL_LEN - TCP_LEN - IP_LEN)
414     hdr.tcp_copy.dataOffset = hdr.tcp.dataOffset;
415     hdr.tcp_copy.res = hdr.tcp.res;
416     hdr.tcp_copy.flags_1 = hdr.tcp.flags_1;
417     hdr.tcp_copy.flags_2 = hdr.tcp.flags_2;
418     hdr.tcp_copy.flags_3 = hdr.tcp.flags_3;
419     hdr.tcp_copy.window = hdr.tcp.window;
420     hdr.tcp_copy.checksum = hdr.tcp.checksum;       //
Will be recalculated
421     hdr.tcp_copy.urgentPtr = hdr.tcp.urgentPtr;
422     hdr.tcp_copy.options = hdr.tcp.options;
423
424     //New payload
425     //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.setValid();
426     //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.payload = payload; // New Payload 28 30 29
(0)
427
428     hdr.tcp_payload.payload_start = payload_start; // (
429     hdr.tcp_payload.payload_match = payload_match; // 0)000
430
431     //meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length_in_bytes_2=meta.tcp_metadata.
payload_length_in_bytes + 7;
432     //hdr.tcp_payload_2.payload[meta.tcp_metadata.
payload_length_in_bytes_2:meta.tcp_metadata.payload_length_in_bytes] =
payload_end;
433
434     //hdr.tcp_payload_mod_long.setValid();
435     //hdr.tcp_payload_mod_long.payload[255:232] = payload; // New

```

```

Payload 28 30 29 (0)
436
437 // Set the metadata to 1 to mark the pkt to recalculate checksum
438 meta.modified = 0x1;
439
440 // Update egress_port
441 standard_metadata.egress_spec = port;
442 }
443
444
445 //action tcp_forward_2 (payload_table_t payload) {
446 //hdr.tcp_payload.payload = payload; // payload='s['
447 //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.payload = payload;
448 //hdr.tcp_payload.payload = payload; // payload='sicc '
449
450 //hdr.tcp.setValid();
451 //hdr.tcp_payload.setInvalid();
452 //hdr.tcp_payload_2.setInvalid();
453 //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.setValid();
454
455 //hdr.tcp_payload_mod.payload = payload; // payload='sicc '
456 //meta.modified = 0x1;
457 //hdr.ipv4.totalLen = IPV4.LEN_mod;
458 //hdr.ipv4.identification = hdr.ipv4.identification + 2;
459 //}
460
461 table tcp_exact {
462     key = {
463         hdr.tcp_payload.payload_match : exact; //match for 2.063
464         //matching on substring is not really liked by the P4 compiler
465         //meta.udp_payload_beginning: exact; // match the cica at the,
and later add the rest of the payload
466     }
467
468     actions = {

```

```

469         tcp_forward_hack;
470         //tcp_forward_2;
471         NoAction;
472     }
473     size = 1024;
474     default_action = NoAction;
475
476     //const entries = {
477         //0x636963610a : tcp_forward_hack(); // match for cica
478         //0x63696361 : udp_forward_hack(); // match for cica +++++
479     //}
480 }
481
482
483
484 apply {
485     if (hdr.ipv4.isValid()) {
486         ipv4_lpm.apply();
487     }
488     if (hdr.udp.isValid()) {
489         udp_exact.apply();
490     }
491     if (hdr.tcp.isValid()) {
492         tcp_exact.apply();
493     }
494 }
495 }
496
497 /******
498 ***** EGRESS PROCESSING *****
499 *****/
500
501 control MyEgress(inout headers hdr,
502                 inout metadata meta,
503                 inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {

```

```
504
505
506     /*action update_port(bit<9> port) {
507         standard_metadata.egress_spec = port;
508     }
509     action drop() {
510         mark_to_drop();
511     }
512     table port_match {
513         key = {
514             meta.modified: exact;
515         }
516         actions = {
517             update_port;
518             NoAction;
519             drop;
520         }
521         size = 256;
522     }
523     apply {
524         port_match.apply();
525     }*/
526
527
528     action ipv4_eforward(macAddr_t dstAddr, egressSpec_t port) {
529         standard_metadata.egress_spec = port;
530         hdr.ethernet.srcAddr = hdr.ethernet.dstAddr;
531         hdr.ethernet.dstAddr = dstAddr;
532         hdr.ipv4.ttl = hdr.ipv4.ttl - 1;
533         hdr.ipv4.identification = 0;
534         meta.modified = 0x0;
535     }
536
537     action drop() {
538         mark_to_drop();
```

```

539     }
540
541     table ipv4_elpm {
542         key = {
543             hdr.ipv4.dstAddr: lpm;
544         }
545         actions = {
546             ipv4_eforward;
547             drop;
548             NoAction;
549         }
550         size = 1024;
551         default_action = drop();
552     }
553
554     apply {
555         ipv4_elpm.apply();
556     }
557
558 }
559
560 /******
561 *****      CHECKSUM      COMPUTATION      *****
562 *****/
563
564 control MyComputeChecksum(inout headers  hdr, inout metadata meta) {
565     apply {
566         //Normal IP
567         update_checksum(
568             (hdr.ipv4.isValid() && meta.modified == 0x0),
569             { hdr.ipv4.version ,
570             hdr.ipv4.ihl ,
571             hdr.ipv4.diffserv ,
572             hdr.ipv4.totalLen ,
573             hdr.ipv4.identification ,

```

```
574         hdr.ipv4.flags ,
575         hdr.ipv4.fragOffset ,
576         hdr.ipv4.ttl ,
577         hdr.ipv4.protocol ,
578         hdr.ipv4.srcAddr ,
579         hdr.ipv4.dstAddr } ,
580     hdr.ipv4.hdrChecksum ,
581     HashAlgorithm.csum16);
582
583 //NEW IP
584 update_checksum (
585     (hdr.ipv4_copy.isValid() && meta.modified == 0x1) ,
586     { hdr.ipv4_copy.version ,
587     hdr.ipv4_copy.ihl ,
588     hdr.ipv4_copy.diffserv ,
589     hdr.ipv4_copy.totalLen ,
590     //payload.LEN_mod ,
591     hdr.ipv4_copy.identification ,
592     hdr.ipv4_copy.flags ,
593     hdr.ipv4_copy.fragOffset ,
594     hdr.ipv4_copy.ttl ,
595     hdr.ipv4_copy.protocol ,
596     hdr.ipv4_copy.srcAddr ,
597     hdr.ipv4_copy.dstAddr } ,
598     hdr.ipv4_copy.hdrChecksum ,
599     HashAlgorithm.csum16);
600
601
602 //UDP header checksum
603 update_checksum (
604     (hdr.udp.isValid() && meta.modified == 0x1) ,
605     {   hdr.ipv4.srcAddr ,
606     hdr.ipv4.dstAddr ,
607     8w0 ,
608     hdr.ipv4.protocol ,
```

```
609         hdr.udp.len ,
610         hdr.udp.srcPort ,
611         hdr.udp.dstPort ,
612         hdr.udp.len ,
613         hdr.udp.payload
614     },
615     hdr.udp.checksum ,
616     HashAlgorithm.csum16);
617
618     //TCP header checksum
619     update_checksum_with_payload (
620         (hdr.tcp_copy.isValid() && hdr.ipv4_copy.protocol == TCP_TYPE && meta
621         .modified == 0x1),
622         {   hdr.ipv4_copy.srcAddr ,
623             hdr.ipv4_copy.dstAddr ,
624             8w0,
625             hdr.ipv4_copy.protocol ,
626             meta.tcp_metadata.tcp_header_length_for_checksum ,
627             hdr.tcp_copy.srcPort ,
628             hdr.tcp_copy.dstPort ,
629             hdr.tcp_copy.seqNo ,
630             hdr.tcp_copy.ackNo ,
631             hdr.tcp_copy.dataOffset ,
632             hdr.tcp_copy.res ,
633             hdr.tcp_copy.flags_1 ,
634             hdr.tcp_copy.flags_2 ,
635             hdr.tcp_copy.flags_3 ,
636             hdr.tcp_copy.window ,
637             hdr.tcp_copy.urgentPtr ,
638             hdr.tcp_copy.options ,
639             hdr.tcp_payload.payload_start ,
640             hdr.tcp_payload.payload_match ,
641             hdr.tcp_payload_2.payload
642         },
643         hdr.tcp_copy.checksum ,
```

```

643     HashAlgorithm.csum16);
644 }
645 }
646
647 /******
648 *****  D E P A R S E R  *****
649 *****/
650
651 control MyDeparser(packet_out packet, in headers hdr) {
652     apply {
653         packet.emit(hdr.ethernet);
654         packet.emit(hdr.ipv4);
655         packet.emit(hdr.udp);
656         packet.emit(hdr.tcp);
657         packet.emit(hdr.ethernet_copy);
658         packet.emit(hdr.ipv4_copy);
659         packet.emit(hdr.tcp_copy);
660         packet.emit(hdr.tcp_payload);
661         packet.emit(hdr.tcp_payload_2);
662         //packet.emit(hdr.tcp_payload_mod);
663     }
664 }
665
666 /******
667 *****  S W I T C H  *****
668 *****/
669
670 V1Switch(
671     MyParser(),
672     MyVerifyChecksum(),
673     MyIngress(),
674     MyEgress(),
675     MyComputeChecksum(),
676     MyDeparser()

```

```
677 ) main ;
```

Listing B.1: Robot P4 code

Appendix C

Measuring TCP RTT

C.1 P4 RTT Code

```
1 #include <core.p4>
2 #include <vlmodel.p4>
3
4 /* size of timestamp (microseconds) */
5 #define TIMESTAMP_BITS 48
6 /* size of flow_id */
7 #define FLOWID_BITS 128
8
9 /*use to toggle support for deterministic subsampling */
10 #define SUBSAMPLE_FLAG
11
12 /* use to toggle support to avoid counting delayed ACKs */
13 // #define MSS_FLAG
14
15 /* define the number of tables MULTITABLE == 2 */
16 #define MULTITABLE 2
17
18 /* if tracking MSS */
19 #ifdef MSS_FLAG
20 /* size of MSS */
```

```
21 #define MSSID_BITS 96
22 #endif
23
24 /* ipv4 type header */
25 const bit<16> TYPE_IPV4 = 0x800;
26 /* tcp type header */
27 const bit<8> TYPE_TCP = 0x6;
28
29 /* maximum number of rtt's to track */
30 const bit<32> MAX_NUM_RTT_S = 1024;
31
32 /* syn flag header */
33 #ifdef MSS_FLAG
34 const bit<1> SYN_FLAG = 1w1;
35 #endif
36
37 /* number of timestamps to tables */
38 const bit<32> TABLE_SIZE = 120;
39
40 /* table to store MSS for flows*/
41 #ifdef MSS_FLAG
42 const bit<32> MSS_TABLE_SIZE = 32w1000;
43 #endif
44
45 /* set number of hash tables */
46 #ifdef MULTITABLE
47 // a little unclear, would prefer 32w{MULTITABLE}
48 const bit<32> NUM_TABLES = (bit<32>) MULTITABLE;
49 #else
50 const bit<32> NUM_TABLES = 32w1;
51 #endif
52
53 /* handle drop index */
54 const bit<32> DROP_INDEX = NUM_TABLES;
55 /* calculate size of register of hash tables */
```

```

56 const bit<32> REGISTER_SIZE = TABLE_SIZE * (NUM_TABLES+1); //+1 for drop
    table
57
58 /* default mss */
59 const bit<32> DEFAULT_MSS = 32w1460;
60
61
62 /******
63 ***** H E A D E R S *****
64 *****/
65
66 typedef bit<9> egressSpec_t;
67 typedef bit<48> macAddr_t;
68 typedef bit<32> ip4Addr_t;
69
70 /* Ethernet header */
71 header ethernet_t {
72     macAddr_t dstAddr;
73     macAddr_t srcAddr;
74     bit<16> etherType;
75 }
76
77 /* ipv4 header */
78 header ipv4_t {
79     bit<4> version;
80     bit<4> ihl;
81     bit<8> diffserv;
82     bit<16> totalLen;
83     bit<16> identification;
84     bit<3> flags;
85     bit<13> fragOffset;
86     bit<8> ttl;
87     bit<8> protocol;
88     bit<16> hdrChecksum;
89     ip4Addr_t srcAddr;

```

```
90     ip4Addr_t dstAddr;
91 }
92
93 /* TCP Header */
94 header tcp_t {
95     bit <16> srcPort;
96     bit <16> dstPort;
97     bit <32> seqNo;
98     bit <32> ackNo;
99     bit <4> dataOffset;
100    bit <3> res;
101    bit <3> ecn;
102    bit <1> urg;
103    bit <1> ack;
104    bit <1> psh;
105    bit <1> rst;
106    bit <1> syn;
107    bit <1> fin;
108    bit <16> window;
109    bit <16> checksum;
110    bit <16> urgentPtr;
111 }
112
113
114 #ifdef MSS_FLAG
115 /* TCP Options */
116 /* For now we are assuming static the MSS option is immediately after the
117 TCP header for all SYN packets */
118 header tcp_mss_option_t {
119     bit <8> kind;
120     bit <8> len;
121     bit <16> mss;
122 }
123 #endif
124
```

```

125 struct metadata {
126     /* flow id */
127     bit<FLOWID_BITS> flowID;
128     /* hash of flow */
129     bit<32> hash_key;
130     /* expected ack hash */
131     bit<32> eACK;
132     /* size of packet payload */
133     bit<32> payload_size;
134
135     #ifdef MSS.FLAG
136     //separate identifier for MSS table
137     bit<MSSID_BITS> mssID;
138     bit<32> mss_key;
139     #endif
140
141     #ifdef SUBSAMPLE.FLAG
142     //p4-16 runtime doesn't allow boolean values in header/metadata
143     /* flag if packet is being sampled */
144     bit<1> sampled;
145     #endif
146 }
147
148
149 struct headers {
150     ethernet_t    ethernet;
151     ipv4_t        ipv4;
152     tcp_t         tcp;
153     #ifdef MSS.FLAG
154     tcp_mss_option_t mss;
155     #endif
156 }
157
158
159 /******

```

```
160 ***** R E G I S T E R S *****
161 *****/
162
163 /* register array to store timestamps */
164 register <bit <TIMESTAMP_BITS>>(REGISTER_SIZE) timestamps;
165 register <bit <FLOWID_BITS>>(REGISTER_SIZE) keys;
166
167 #ifdef MSS.FLAG
168 /* store mss of packet flows in table */
169 register <bit <16>>(MSS_TABLE_SIZE) four_tuple_mss_table;
170 #endif
171
172 /* register for current RTT register index */
173 register <bit <32>>(1) current_rtt_index;
174
175 /* register/array to store RTTs in the order they are computed */
176 register <bit <TIMESTAMP_BITS>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) rtt;
177 register <bit <32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) register_indices_of_rtt;
178 register <bit <32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) src_ips_of_rtt;
179 register <bit <32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) dst_ips_of_rtt;
180 register <bit <16>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) src_ports_of_rtt;
181 register <bit <16>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) dst_ports_of_rtt;
182 register <bit <32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) seq_nos_of_rtt;
183 register <bit <32>>(MAX_NUMRTTS) ack_nos_of_rtt;
184
185 /* registers for tunable parameters */
186 register <bit <TIMESTAMP_BITS>>(1) latency_threshold;
187
188
189 #ifdef SUBSAMPLE.FLAG
190 //0% means all packets will be sampled
191 register <bit <16>>(1) filter_percent;
192 #endif
193
194
```

```
195  /******  
196  ***** P A R S E R *****  
197  *****/  
198  
199  parser MyParser(packet_in packet ,  
200                out headers hdr ,  
201                inout metadata meta ,  
202                inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {  
203  
204      state start {  
205        transition parse_ethernet;  
206      }  
207  
208      /* parse ethernet header */  
209      state parse_ethernet {  
210        packet.extract(hdr.ethernet);  
211        transition select(hdr.ethernet.etherType) {  
212          TYPE_IPV4: parse_ipv4;  
213          default: accept;  
214        }  
215      }  
216  
217      /* parse ipv4 header */  
218      state parse_ipv4 {  
219        packet.extract(hdr.ipv4);  
220        /* check to see if tcp packet */  
221        transition select(hdr.ipv4.protocol) {  
222          TYPE_TCP: parse_tcp;  
223          default: accept;  
224        }  
225      }  
226  
227      /* parse tcp header */  
228      state parse_tcp {  
229        packet.extract(hdr.tcp);
```

```

230     transition select(hdr.tcp.syn){
231         #ifdef MSS.FLAG
232             SYN.FLAG : parse_mss;
233         #endif
234         //everything else including ACKs
235         default: accept;
236     }
237
238 }
239
240 #ifdef MSS.FLAG
241 /* parse static MSS option*/
242 state parse_mss {
243     packet.extract(hdr.mss);
244     transition accept;
245 }
246 #endif
247
248 }
249
250 /******
251 *****      C H E C K S U M   V E R I F I C A T I O N      *****
252 *****/
253
254 control MyVerifyChecksum(inout headers hdr, inout metadata meta) {
255     apply { }
256 }
257
258
259 /******
260 *****      I N G R E S S   P R O C E S S I N G      *****
261 *****/
262
263
264 control MyIngress(inout headers hdr,

```

```

265     inout metadata meta,
266     inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {
267
268     /* calculate payload of tcp packet */
269     action set_payload_size() {
270         meta.payload_size = ((bit<32>)(hdr.ipv4.totalLen - (((bit<16>) hdr.ipv4.
271             ihl) + ((bit<16>)hdr.tcp.dataOffset)) * 16w4)));
272
273     /* set expected ACK */
274     action set_eACK() {
275         meta.eACK = hdr.tcp.seqNo + meta.payload_size;
276     }
277
278     /* save metadata tuple */
279     action set_flowID(bool isOutgoing){
280         if(isOutgoing){
281             meta.flowID = hdr.ipv4.srcAddr ++ hdr.ipv4.dstAddr ++ hdr.tcp.srcPort
282             ++ hdr.tcp.dstPort ++ meta.eACK;
283         }else{
284             meta.flowID = hdr.ipv4.dstAddr ++ hdr.ipv4.srcAddr ++ hdr.tcp.dstPort
285             ++ hdr.tcp.srcPort ++ hdr.tcp.ackNo;
286         }
287     }
288
289     /* hash tuple into key */
290     action set_key() {
291         hash(meta.hash_key,
292             HashAlgorithm.crc32,
293             32w0,
294             {meta.flowID},
295             TABLE_SIZE);
296     }

```

```

297 #ifdef MSS.FLAG
298 /* set the 4 tuple for the maximum segment size storing register */
299 action set_mssID () {
300     meta.mssID = hdr.ipv4.dstAddr ++ hdr.ipv4.srcAddr ++ hdr.tcp.dstPort ++
301     hdr.tcp.srcPort ;
302 }
303 /* hash the 4 tuple into an index */
304 action set_mss_key () {
305     hash (meta.mss_key ,
306         HashAlgorithm.crc32 ,
307         32w0 ,
308         {meta.mssID} ,
309         MSS_TABLE_SIZE) ;
310 }
311 #endif
312
313 /* set MSS for SYN packets for each 4 tuple */
314 /* ideally we would have perfect hashing or dynamic hash table , because the
315    MSS value is necessary
316    for proper operation of the rest of this approach.
317 */
318 action push_mss () {
319     #ifdef MSS.FLAG
320     set_mssID () ;
321     set_mss_key () ;
322
323     four_tuple_mss_table.write (meta.mss_key , hdr.mss.mss) ;
324     #endif
325 }
326
327 #ifdef SUBSAMPLE.FLAG
328 /* determine if a packet should be sampled based on the crc32 hash */
329 action to_be_sampled () {

```

```
330     bit<16> sample_key = 16w100;
331     hash(sample_key ,
332         HashAlgorithm.crc16 ,
333         16w0,
334         {meta.flowID} ,
335         16w100);
336
337     bit<16> fp = 16w0;
338     filter_percent.read(fp , 0);
339
340     if(sample_key >= fp){
341         meta.sampled = 1w1;
342     }else{
343         meta.sampled = 1w0;
344     }
345
346 }
347 #endif
348
349
350 /* push timestamp into tables with hashed key as index */
351 action push_outgoing_timestamp(){
352     set_payload_size();
353     set_eACK();
354     set_flowID(true);
355     set_key();
356
357     #ifdef MSS_FLAG
358     set_mssID();
359     set_mss_key();
360     #endif
361
362     bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> outgoing_timestamp;
363     bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> lt;
364
```

```

365 latency_threshold.read(lt, 0);
366
367 //default is one table
368 bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> time_diff0 = lt;
369
370 #if MULTITABLE > 1
371 bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> time_diff1 = lt;
372 #endif
373
374 //hardcoded for up to 4 tables
375 //calculate the time difference between the current time and each of the
existing timestamps at that index
376 //for each table
377 bit<32> offset = 32w0;
378 timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key + offset);
379 if (outgoing_timestamp != 0) {
380     time_diff0 = standard_metadata.ingress_global_timestamp -
outgoing_timestamp;
381 }
382
383 #if MULTITABLE > 1
384 offset = TABLE_SIZE;
385 timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key + offset);
386 if (outgoing_timestamp != 0) {
387     time_diff1 = standard_metadata.ingress_global_timestamp -
outgoing_timestamp;
388 }
389 #endif
390
391 if(time_diff0 < lt){ //no stale packet in table 1
392     offset = TABLE_SIZE;
393     #if MULTITABLE > 1
394     if(time_diff1 < lt){ //no stale packet in table 2
395         offset = TABLE_SIZE * 2;
396     }

```

```

397     #endif //MULTITABLE > 1
398 }else{
399     offset = 32w0; //insert into table 1
400 }
401
402 #ifdef MSS.FLAG
403 //only allow packets that are full sized (=MSS) to be processed
404 bit<16> mss;
405 four_tuple_mss_table.read(mss, meta.mss_key);
406 if((mss != 16w0 && meta.payload_size != (bit<32>) mss) || meta.
payload_size != DEFAULT_MSS){
407     offset = TABLE_SIZE * DROP_INDX;
408 }
409 #else
410 //only allow packets with at least a byte of payload
411 if(meta.payload_size == 32w0){
412     offset = TABLE_SIZE * DROP_INDX;
413 }
414 #endif
415
416
417 #ifdef SUBSAMPLE.FLAG
418 to_be_sampled();
419 if(meta.sampled == 1w0){
420     offset = TABLE_SIZE * DROP_INDX;
421 }
422 #endif
423
424 //write to appropriate table at index
425 timestamps.write(meta.hash_key+offset, standard_metadata.
ingress_global_timestamp);
426 keys.write(meta.hash_key+offset, meta.flowID);
427 }
428
429 /* read timestamp from table and subtract from current time to get rtt*/

```

```

430  action get_rtt() {
431      set_flowID(false);
432      set_key();
433
434      bit<32> offset = TABLE_SIZE * DROP_INDX;
435      bit<FLOWID_BITS> rflowID;
436
437      bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> rtt;
438      bit<32> rtt_index;
439      bit<TIMESTAMP_BITS> outgoing_timestamp;
440
441      //update index by going backwards through tables
442
443      #if MULTITABLE > 1
444      keys.read(rflowID, meta.hash_key+TABLE_SIZE);
445      timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key+TABLE_SIZE);
446      if(rflowID == meta.flowID && outgoing_timestamp != 0){
447          offset = TABLE_SIZE;
448      }
449      #endif
450
451      //default is one table
452      keys.read(rflowID, meta.hash_key);
453      timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key);
454      if(rflowID == meta.flowID && outgoing_timestamp != 0){
455          offset = 0;
456      }
457
458      timestamps.read(outgoing_timestamp, meta.hash_key + offset);
459      rtt = standard_metadata.ingress_global_timestamp - outgoing_timestamp;
460
461
462
463      #ifdef SUBSAMPLE_FLAG
464      to_be_sampled();

```

```

465     if(meta.sampled == 1w0){ //false
466         offset = TABLE_SIZE * DROP_INDX;
467     }
468 #endif
469
470 // For debugging purposes, write RTT to source MAC address if available
471 if(offset < TABLE_SIZE*DROP_INDX){
472     hdr.ethernet.srcAddr = rtt;
473 }else{
474     hdr.ethernet.srcAddr = 48w0;
475 }
476
477 // Write RTT to rtts register
478 current_rtt_index.read(rtt_index, 0);
479 rtts.write(rtt_index, rtt);
480 register_indices_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, meta.hash_key + offset);
481 src_ips_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.ipv4.srcAddr);
482 dst_ips_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.ipv4.dstAddr);
483 src_ports_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.srcPort);
484 dst_ports_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.dstPort);
485 seq_nos_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.seqNo);
486 ack_nos_of_rtts.write(rtt_index, hdr.tcp.ackNo);
487 current_rtt_index.write(0, (rtt_index + 1) % MAX_NUM_RTT);
488
489 // Set timestamp to 0
490 timestamps.write(meta.hash_key + offset, 0);
491
492 }
493
494 /* drop irrelevant packets */
495 action drop() {
496     mark_to_drop();
497 }
498
499 /* handle ACK packets */

```

```
500  action handle_ack() {
501      push_outgoing_timestamp();
502      get_rtt();
503  }
504
505  table tcp_flag_syn_match {
506      key = {
507          hdr.tcp.syn: exact;
508      }
509      actions = {
510          push_mss;
511          NoAction;
512      }
513      size = 2;
514      default_action = NoAction();
515  }
516
517  table tcp_flag_ack_match {
518      key = {
519          hdr.tcp.ack: exact;
520      }
521      actions = {
522          push_outgoing_timestamp;
523          handle_ack;
524          NoAction;
525      }
526      size = 2;
527      default_action = push_outgoing_timestamp();
528  }
529
530  action ipv4_forward(macAddr_t dstAddr, egressSpec_t port) {
531      standard_metadata.egress_spec = port;
532      hdr.ethernet.srcAddr = hdr.ethernet.dstAddr;
533      hdr.ethernet.dstAddr = dstAddr;
534      hdr.ipv4.ttl = hdr.ipv4.ttl - 1;
```

```

535     }
536
537     table ipv4_lpm {
538         key = {
539             hdr.ipv4.dstAddr: lpm;
540         }
541         actions = {
542             ipv4_forward;
543             drop;
544             NoAction;
545         }
546         size = 1024;
547         default_action = drop();
548     }
549
550     apply {
551         if (hdr.ipv4.isValid()) {
552             ipv4_lpm.apply();
553         }
554         if (hdr.tcp.isValid()) {
555             if (hdr.tcp.rst != 1w1) {
556                 tcp_flag_syn_match.apply();
557                 tcp_flag_ack_match.apply();
558             } else {
559                 drop();
560             }
561         }
562     }
563 }
564
565 /******
566 ***** EGRESS PROCESSING *****
567 *****/
568
569 control MyEgress(inout headers hdr,

```

```

570     inout metadata meta,
571     inout standard_metadata_t standard_metadata) {
572   apply { }
573 }
574
575 /*****
576 ***** CHECKSUM COMPUTATION *****
577 *****/
578
579 control MyComputeChecksum(inout headers hdr, inout metadata meta) {
580   apply {
581     update_checksum(
582       hdr.ipv4.isValid(),
583       { hdr.ipv4.version,
584         hdr.ipv4.ihl,
585         hdr.ipv4.diffserv,
586         hdr.ipv4.totalLen,
587         hdr.ipv4.identification,
588         hdr.ipv4.flags,
589         hdr.ipv4.fragOffset,
590         hdr.ipv4.ttl,
591         hdr.ipv4.protocol,
592         hdr.ipv4.srcAddr,
593         hdr.ipv4.dstAddr },
594       hdr.ipv4.hdrChecksum,
595       HashAlgorithm.csum16);
596   }
597 }
598
599 /*****
600 ***** DEPARSER *****
601 *****/
602
603 control MyDeparser(packet_out packet, in headers hdr) {
604   apply {

```

```
605     packet.emit(hdr.ethernet);
606     packet.emit(hdr.ipv4);
607     packet.emit(hdr.tcp);
608     #ifdef MSS_FLAG
609     packet.emit(hdr.mss);
610     #endif
611 }
612 }
613
614 /*****
615 ***** SWITCH *****
616 *****/
617
618 V1Switch(
619 MyParser(),
620 MyVerifyChecksum(),
621 MyIngress(),
622 MyEgress(),
623 MyComputeChecksum(),
624 MyDeparser()
625 ) main;
```

Listing C.1: RTT P4 code